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**Universities and Libraries as Commons-Based Innovative
Environments for learning, civic engagement and democracy**

LibCommon

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WP2: D2.2

Comparative background analysis

This publication is the result of a collaborative effort among the four partner organizations participating in the project, coordinated and edited by University of Lille (Antoine Henry).

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Introduction

The purpose of WP2 is to assess the state of the art in the field of LibCommon and to identify gaps, issues or pain points that are going to be addressed through the project. Within this WP, task 2.2 is about analysing project objectives through comparative background research, including compiling relevant services, summarizing reports, identifying experts, interviewing policymakers, and outlining effective approaches. A SWOT analysis will be used to identify key action areas, formulate recommendations, and provide insights for developing a comprehensive model. Task 2.2 is complementary to task 2.1 that builds a literature review of the topic. By combining academic literature, reports, documentation and interviews, we will have a clear understanding of the situation.

This report aims to clarify the objectives and propose actionable recommendations for enhancing the role of public libraries in fostering education, social inclusion, and democratic participation across Europe. Drawing on the historical and socio-political significance of libraries as spaces for equitable access to knowledge, this study examines their evolving functions in addressing contemporary educational and social needs. By synthesizing national and regional reports, mapping expert networks, and engaging policymakers, the report identifies key challenges and opportunities for libraries in supporting learning, community engagement, and digital inclusivity. The analysis focuses on three core dimensions: (1) the cataloguing of library services and their alignment with educational and social priorities, (2) the role of libraries in bridging digital divides and promoting inclusive digital practices, and (3) the strategic integration of teaching and learning approaches to empower communities.

Outcomes from the task are the following:

- contributions to the creation of a dedicated framework to have a different understanding of the role of libraries as learning and educational commons, participatory planning of space, self-learning, community empowerment and well-being through the collaboration of universities and libraries, civic engagement, social inclusion, and youth.
- contribution to the further syllabus for the training course (see T2.5)

The current report (D2.2) is to present the analysis of the situation within three countries from the consortium: Greece, Spain and France. The report proceeds as follows: we will go through each case and the last section will synthesize outcomes from the three cases and will provide an analysis of the situation.

To achieve this task, partners did for each case:

- a review of reports, documentation, a series of interviews with librarians or people associated with policymaking;
- interviews with international experts and practitioners to contrast.

Table 1 summarizes the work done by each partner

Interviewee	Position and institution	Partner
Dr. Anthi Katsirikou	President of the Association of Greek Librarians and Information Scientists, and Head of the Library at the University of Piraeus	UTh
Dr. Giannis Tsakonas	Director of the Library and Information Center at the University of Patras, Vice President of the international organization LIBER, and member of its Executive Board.	UTh
Damiana Koutsomicha	Head of the 'Dimitris & Aliko Perrotis' Library. She graduated from the Department of Library Science at ATEITH and holds an MScEcon in Library and Information Services Management from Aberystwyth University, Wales.	UTh
Giannis Farsaris	Professor of Informatics, author, and founder of the Digital Open Library (www.openbook.gr). He is also a lecturer in seminars on artificial intelligence and actively involved in the fields of Digital Commons and creative freedom on the Internet.	UTh
Núria Pérez and Txell Solà	Social Educators and educators at the communitarian Montseny Library (Vic) in which she works with children from disadvantaged background	UVIC
Ignasi Jané	BA in Humanities. Director of Pilarín Bayés public library in Vic and head of Culture Department at Vic Local Government	UVIC
Gemma Mascaró and Montse Aguilar	Librarians. Director of the Library of the University of Vic and Librarian and	UVIC

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	Head of customer service at the library of the University of Vic	
Trini Molist and Albert Ribes	Social Educator. Coordinator of the Library of Things developed among local associations and NGOs in Vic and Social Educator and Educator at the Library of Things developed among local associations and NGOs in Vic.	UVIC
Marta Cano; Enric Vilagrossa and Albert Cano	Librarian. General Manager of the Barcelona County network of public libraries (Xarxa de Biblioteques de la Diputació de Barcelona); Economist. Head of unit of planification of the Barcelona County network of libraries; and Sociologist. Head of unit of quality and data analysis of the Barcelona County network of libraries (Xarxa de Biblioteques de la Diputació de Barcelona)	UVIC
Dr. Nicolás Barbieri	Professor at the Open University of Catalonia. Expert on libraries and democratic culture.	UVIC
Dr. Natalia Duque Cardona	Professor at the University of Antioquia (Colombia). International Contrast interview.	UVIC
Sandra Zuluaga	Leader of the initiative 'Ratón de biblioteca'. Medellín, Colombian. International Contrast interview.	UVIC
Tatiana Sanches	Head of the library of the Faculty of Psychology and Education. University of Lisboa. International Contrast Interview.	UVIC
Julien Roche	Director of the ULille Research Library. He is also head of LIBER, the Association of European Research Libraries	ULille.
Laure Delrue	Co-director of the ULille Research Library.	ULille

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Hélène Brochard	Director of the Villeneuve d'Ascq Library.	ULille
Julien Maréchal	Director of the Petite Bibliothèque Ronde (Clamart, France).	ULille
Silvère Mercier	Former librarian and co-founder of the association Savoircom1	ULille
Malick Diallo	Director of the Rennes Métropole Area Library. Vice-director of the French National Librarian Association.	ULille

Table 1: overview of all the interviews done by each partner.

In relation to this aim, it is clear that, in the general context, public libraries are presented as key agents of universal access to knowledge, cultural participation and community cohesion. This presentation is in line with the Manifesto's idea that 'the public library represents a local gateway to knowledge, provides a basic condition for lifelong learning, independent decision-making and cultural development of the individual and social groups' (IFLA, 2022, p. 1). The various projects outlined in the following sections are examples of how libraries ensure universal accessibility to library services, such as mobile libraries or inclusive initiatives aimed at groups with specific needs. It is also noted that the projects developed in the library's framework show, along the same lines as the Manifesto, a clear desire to strengthen 'healthy knowledge societies through providing access to and enabling the creation and sharing of knowledge of all sorts' (*Ibid.*)

The results of the interviews offer a broad view of the functioning and objectives of the libraries in the region, showing their strengths and current challenges, which are contrasted and complemented with contributions from international contexts to a very diverse and vulnerable population that experiences violence and precarious situations in their daily lives. The contributions of the different people interviewed have been triangulated and, subsequently, the results have been structured into four main areas: (a) the Role of Libraries in Learning and Education; (b) Participation and Democratic Culture, including Social Inclusion and Equal Access; (c) Spatial Design and Shared Spaces; (d) finally, Digital Technologies and Information Access.

A SWOT analysis is conducted to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats faced by libraries, informing priority areas for action. The findings are synthesized to develop a comprehensive model that aligns with the Erasmus +

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objectives, emphasizing collaboration between libraries, educators, policymakers, and communities. This report serves as a critical input for shaping a sustainable, inclusive, and democratic future for public libraries across Europe.

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Case – GREECE

This research was based on an extensive review and analysis of existing bibliographic sources and reports concerning the current state of libraries in Greece. In addition, a qualitative approach was followed through semi-structured interviews with four professionals in leadership positions in Greek libraries, which were conducted in April 2025 remotely (via video calls) and analysed thematically. Each interview lasted approximately one and a half hours. The objective was to record and analyse their perspectives and assessments regarding the condition and prospects of libraries in Greece, based on the four key axes defined by the LibCommon project:

- a) The role of libraries in learning and education,
- b) The role of libraries in participation and democratic culture, including social inclusion and equal access,
- c) Spatial design and shared spaces,
- d) Digital technologies and information access.

The interviews were conducted with the following distinguished professionals in Greece, notable for their contributions to libraries:

- Dr. Anthi Katsirikou – President of the Association of Greek Librarians and Information Scientists, and Head of the Library at the University of Piraeus.
- Dr. Giannis Tsakonas – Director of the Library and Information Center at the University of Patras, Vice President of the international organization LIBER, and member of its Executive Board.
- Damiana Koutsomicha – Head of the ‘Dimitris & Aliko Perrotis’ Library. She graduated from the Department of Library Science at ATEITH and holds an MScEcon in Library and Information Services Management from Aberystwyth University, Wales.
- Giannis Farsaris – Professor of Informatics, author, and founder of the Digital Open Library¹. He is also a lecturer in seminars on artificial intelligence and actively involved in the fields of Digital Commons and creative freedom on the Internet.

1. General Context

In recent years, the role of libraries has been reshaped to respond to the continuously evolving social, technological, and educational challenges. This evolution has increased interest in studying the functioning of libraries within the Greek context, especially in relation to broader European standards and values, as well as in

¹ www.openbook.gr

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connection with initiatives such as the European LibCommon project. This project aims to highlight libraries and their functions, including within the Greek context, not only as agents of knowledge, participation, and social cohesion, but also as commons: collectively, openly, and democratically managed institutions.

The Current Landscape of Greek Libraries

Libraries in Greece have over the years played an essential role in enhancing access to knowledge, cultivating reading habits and supporting educational and cultural life. They are one of the few public spaces that offers free access to information, empowering both local communities and individuals. At the same time, efforts are being made to function as cultural and social centres, hosting lifelong learning, creative expression and the integration of vulnerable populations. Physical collections remain a key pillar of access to knowledge, while they are increasingly complemented by initiatives such as digital libraries, which bring content closer to citizens through online distribution. Traditional libraries continue to offer a unique space for study, discovery, and cultural exchange, but are now called upon to integrate elements of the digital age, such as free access to digitized books, educational material, and audio content, in order to meet modern needs.

Despite this significant contribution, libraries in Greece have not been modernized to the extent demanded by contemporary needs. The lack of uniform policy, long-term funding and support has left the library network fragmented, highly unequal and dysfunctional. The situation varies considerably depending on the type of library, its institutional affiliation, local governance and the availability of human and material resources. In this context, it is critical to examine the main types of libraries operating in the country to capture the challenges and opportunities presented by each category.

Municipal Libraries

The municipal libraries² are under the administrative responsibility of the municipalities and constitute an important link in the local cultural fabric. In many cases, they act as the only places of public access to knowledge and information, especially in the regional areas. However, their operation is strongly influenced by the municipal priorities and budgetary possibilities of each local authority. The lack of stable funding, understaffing, and the absence of coordination at the national level have led many of them to underperform or even to complete inactivity. They often rely on volunteers or unskilled staff, while their technological equipment is outdated or non-existent.

² <https://network.nlg.gr/library/>

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Public Libraries

Public libraries are institutionally under the Ministry of Education, Religious Affairs and Sports and constitute a separate and historically important network. Several of them have several valuable documents, archival collections, antiquarian books and local publications, constituting cores of cultural heritage and memory. However, few of them have managed to make substantial progress in modernizing their services and infrastructure. They operate mainly with teachers on secondment, often without library training, and the exploitation of their archival wealth remains largely untapped. The absence of a coherent strategy for their development and insufficient technical and financial support severely limits their ability to adapt to the needs of the digital age.

Academic Libraries

Academic libraries have shown significant signs of progress in recent years. In the context of European funding programmes, through the European Research Funding Framework Programme, they have managed to develop their infrastructure, digitize collections, join scientific networks and offer high quality services to students and researchers. They have invested in staffing, managing scientific repositories and developing research support tools. One of the most important achievements has been the development of collaborative schemes, most notably the Hellenic Academic Libraries Association (HEAL-Link), which provides access to thousands of journals and databases for all Greek universities; the Open Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) of some 58 libraries, where one can search for records of books, journals, conference proceedings, etc. The development of AMELib (Accessible Multi-modal Electronic Library) aims to strengthen the effort to remove barriers for print-disabled users of Greek academic libraries.

At the same time, participation in networks such as OpenAIRE, DOAJ and the creation of institutional repositories have contributed to extroversion, transparency and the enhancement of research output. However, after the end of the relevant funding, their operation is facing serious difficulties. Resources have diminished, human resources are not being renewed, and the prospects for sustainability are becoming uncertain. Nevertheless, thanks to the initiative, expertise and scientific ethos of librarians, many of them continue to operate at a high level of quality. They focus on disseminating open access to knowledge, freely disseminating scientific information, supporting academic integrity and linking with international developments in the field of scientific information.

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Special/Thematic Libraries

Special thematic libraries in Greece focus on specific fields of knowledge or professional specialities, addressing the specialized needs of researchers, professionals, and academics. These libraries may belong to universities, research centres, hospitals, museums, cultural organizations and prisons. Many of them are funded by private initiatives or special programs, allowing them to develop and provide specialized services and high-quality digital resources.

Hospital libraries primarily serve medical and nursing staff, providing access to medical databases, scientific articles, and clinical guidelines. Similarly, museum libraries support research and the management of cultural collections by offering archival material, categorized databases, and educational programs. Prison libraries provide incarcerated individuals with access to books, educational materials, and legal information, supporting literacy, personal development, and rehabilitation. They also offer a constructive outlet that promotes mental well-being and reduces recidivism by encouraging lifelong learning and critical thinking.

Special thematic libraries in Greece are important pillars supporting research and education, offering specialized materials and services tailored to the needs of specific professional and academic communities. Using modern technologies and collaborations at national and international levels, they enhance access to digital resources and promote connections with global knowledge networks. This dynamic enables thematic libraries to evolve into innovation hubs, fostering scientific progress, preservation of cultural heritage, and community development.

National Library of Greece (NLG)

The National Library of Greece³, as the country's leading institutional pillar in the field of librarianship, has undergone a significant transformation in recent years. Its relocation to the Stavros Niarchos Foundation Cultural Centre was accompanied by significant funding and technical support from the Foundation, giving the National Library of Greece the space, means and framework to develop a new vision for its role in modern society. The period of Philipos Tsimpoglou's administration (2014–2023) marked an inspired effort of reform, with an emphasis on transparency, accessibility, democratic functioning, and the creation of an open space for culture and learning. Today, the Library performs essential work in the field of scientific documentation, the preservation of national book production and the strengthening of information literacy, serving as a model for the rest of the country's library network. Despite these

³ <https://www.nlg.gr/static-page/nlg-in-a-nutshell/>

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successes, it still faces challenges, particularly in linking with the school and academic community, but it is clearly one of the most dynamic examples of modernization in the cultural sector of public administration.

School Libraries

The absence of school libraries remains one of the most serious structural deficiencies of the Greek educational system. In many school units, there is neither suitable space nor staff to support the operation of an organized library. Although there have been efforts in the past to create and support school libraries, most initiatives have been abandoned or have been discontinued. Existing books often remain uncatalogued, unsorted and unused, and the lack of systematic integration of literacy and information literacy into the school curriculum is creating a generation of students without adequate information and research skills.

To sum up, the picture of libraries in Greece today is complex and contradictory. On the one hand, there are remarkable efforts, modern infrastructure, and examples of operations that demonstrate what can be achieved when professionalism, knowledge and support are combined. On the other hand, fragmentation, institutional weaknesses, fragmented funding and lack of coherent policy continue to undermine the role of libraries in the country's educational, social and cultural ecosystem.

Public and municipal libraries operate at different speeds, often with inadequate staff and outdated structures, while school libraries remain almost non-existent in terms of systematic operation. Academic libraries, while showing considerable potential for progress, now face serious sustainability challenges. Even the important cultural heritage collections maintained in many public libraries remain largely dormant, without the necessary scientific and technical support.

In this context, the library in Greece continues to rely more on the personal commitment of its people than on an organized national system. However, much potential exists; it remains unstructured. The need to rethink their operation is not just a matter of upgrading infrastructure but is a matter of recognizing their value as institutions of democracy, education and culture. As noted by Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025), Head Librarian at the University of Piraeus and President of the Association of Greek Librarians and Information Scientists:

'Librarians in Greece have often played a foundational role in the development of libraries, even in the absence of any institutional mandate or systemic support. They demonstrate high levels of expertise, flexibility, and technical competence, taking on

responsibilities ranging from managing technological systems and repositories to scheduling academic programmes. They have led key innovations such as open science, information literacy, and makerspaces, often without national policy support, formal recognition, or financial compensation. Moreover, they frequently undertake complex, largely administrative duties that go far beyond the traditional perception of their profession, offering critical organizational solutions within their institutions.'

The Survey on Libraries of Greece (excluding school libraries) is a census survey conducted every two years and it records important information concerning libraries, such as their legal status, the type of the library, the existence of branches and mobile units, collections of books, journals and manuscripts, data on library personnel, facilities and equipment, library traffic and services provided to readers, classification of library material, information on audiovisual material and on the access of the library to electronic documentation over the Internet. According to the survey conducted by The Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT)⁴ that covers all libraries, excluding school libraries, in 2022, the total number of libraries amounted to 347, encompassing the National Library of Greece, 40 public libraries, 139 municipal libraries and 167 libraries of legal persons (under public and private law or in other legal forms) (Graph 1). Out of the total number of libraries, 211 are general libraries and 136 are specialized libraries, most of them being university libraries. These libraries have 148 branches and 38 mobile units.

Graph 1. Number of libraries by legal status, year 2022

⁴ <https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/0b041b93-584b-281e-98b6-64db861d847f>

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2. Analysis of the case

a) Role of Libraries in Learning and Education

1) Overview

The role of libraries in learning and education remains crucial, especially as they are called upon to adapt to the digital and social challenges of our time. The Open Library (Farsaris, 2025) is a characteristic example of such adaptation, offering free digital access to thousands of book titles and audio content. As Giannis Farsaris (2025), its founder, notes: *'The live seminar used to require physical presence, while the modern or asynchronous seminar... breaks geographic boundaries, breaks age and knowledge levels... and solves the issue of time'* highlighting how digital libraries facilitate lifelong learning. In this context, the Open Library, as an open and fully digital initiative, demonstrates how a library can transcend its physical limits and become a tool for inclusive and participatory education. By expanding access to underrepresented groups, such as adult learners, migrants, or individuals with learning difficulties, it meaningfully contributes to educational equity and the democratization of knowledge.

Its example highlights the potential of digital technologies to redefine the role of libraries in modern society. However, such models of operation remain limited within the Greek context. Many Greek libraries still function primarily through physical presence and traditional practices, without having widely adopted digital tools or participatory service models. There is, therefore, an urgent need to transform them into hybrid and multidimensional institutions capable of supporting knowledge dissemination, technological advancement, and citizen participation in culture. Despite chronic shortages in infrastructure, staff, and institutional support, significant efforts are being made to respond to the evolving needs of society. Some libraries stand out for their innovative services and active engagement, but these remain the exception rather than the rule, often sustained by temporary external funding or local initiatives rather than long-term policy integration. The broader picture reveals a landscape of highly uneven service provision, where many libraries operate under conditions of minimal funding and staffing, yet persist in supporting local learning needs.

In this context, Giannis Tsakonas (2025), Deputy Director of the Library & Information Center of the University of Patras and Vice-Chair of the Executive Board of LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries), identifies chronic understaffing as a structural barrier that undermines the ability of academic libraries in Greece to fulfil their social mission. Drawing on his experience both nationally and within European

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research networks, he states: *'We are one-tenth of what we should be. That's the real problem.'* This acute shortage of personnel, especially in large academic libraries that ought to employ 100 to 140 staff members, seriously constraints operations, threatens institutional memory, and puts long-term viability at risk. The departure of experienced professionals without adequate replacement disrupts the transmission of critical operational knowledge and breaks continuity: *'Five people are leaving the libraries... Will there be someone to open them? To open and close them? The order, the knowledge of how things work and don't work, all that will collapse. You can't recover that.'*

For Tsakonas (2025), the problem is not merely operational; it is deeply cultural and institutional. He points to the absence of a library-oriented culture in Greece and the limited respect for libraries as public knowledge institutions: *'We haven't learned to respect libraries. There is no library culture – neither in public discourse nor in institutional practice.'* This systemic neglect affects not only staffing and resources but also the ability of libraries to engage with broader European developments in open access, data management, and citizen science. Although Greek libraries may aspire to such participatory and democratic knowledge models, they remain hindered by insufficient investment: *'There are great ideas – commons, data management, citizen science – but all of these require people. At some point, I consciously stopped engaging. I know these things can't move forward without resources.'*

Public and Municipal Libraries

Public and municipal libraries in Greece strive to meet the cultural and educational needs of local communities. They serve a wide and diverse audience, regardless of age, educational background, or social status. In almost all cases, these libraries provide lending services for printed materials (books, magazines, newspapers) and have children's sections with storytelling and reading promotion activities. Additionally, some organize cultural events, creative workshops, and educational programs that promote lifelong learning.

In recent years, many libraries have offered basic services such as digital literacy workshops, access to computers and the Internet, and assistance with using digital tools and services. They also frequently host cultural events, educational programs, and workshops aimed at various ages and social groups. Through these services, libraries contribute to informing, educating, and socially integrating citizens.

Many of these libraries are staffed by teachers temporarily transferred from schools, often without specialized training in librarianship. Despite limited resources, they harness the creativity and dedication of their staff to implement dynamic educational and social programs. These include STEM workshops, robotics, reading clubs,

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thematic storytelling sessions, and creative writing, transforming the library into a space for collaborative and experiential learning.

University Libraries

University libraries in Greece support teaching and research by providing access to academic sources, databases, and digital material. They also offer quiet study spaces, student equipment, and basic training in the use of information tools. Although many are equipped with modern infrastructure and digital services, the quality and range of services vary significantly across institutions. Greek university libraries have begun to play a significant role in supporting information literacy, digital skills, and lifelong learning, despite long-standing shortages in staffing, financial resources, and technological infrastructure. Several academic libraries offer digital training and integration with academic courses through virtual learning environments (VLEs), for example, the Library of the University of Macedonia in Thessaloniki. Almost all provide educational programs on a fragmented basis; however, only a few have fully structured and credit-bearing information literacy courses. Many librarians emphasize the need for improved infrastructure, increased staffing, and sustainable funding.

The Library of the University of Patras (Figure 1), despite its limited human resources, develops targeted educational activities aimed at strengthening information literacy and familiarizing students with its services. As Giannis Tsakonas (2025) states, *'We don't run educational programs because we don't have the personnel to implement them. There are things we offer... upon request...'* However, the library has integrated a mandatory MOOC-style course for postgraduate students through the e-class platform. This is an automated solution that provides basic training on library use, academic research, and information literacy: *'An assertive move, which seems to be working well, is that through the e-class platform, students starting postgraduate programs are required to take a course, a MOOC, so to speak, offered by the library...'*

Beyond the MOOC, the library also conducts targeted seminars upon request, mostly by instructors of specific postgraduate programs. These are delivered flexibly, even outside standard working hours or on Saturdays: *'Specific professors from specific postgraduate programs ask us to do a seminar on a particular topic. OK, we do it. And we also do it outside standard working hours, and on Saturdays, because we know how postgraduate programs operate.'* The library has also uploaded short instructional videos to its website, aiming to provide immediate support to students. However, as Tsakonas notes, it is not easy to assess the effectiveness of such efforts: *'You never really know how much impact they have... You don't know how many questions have been answered in advance by the content you've proactively created. You can never be sure, because the problem doesn't manifest directly.'*

The overall philosophy of the library is to offer tools and stimuli and to respond flexibly when there is genuine interest. As he concludes: *'We don't proactively and aggressively put ourselves forward, we're more in the logic of small stimuli.'*

Figure 1: Library and Information Centre-Upatras

School Libraries

Although some have organized their collections using databases, their contribution to the learning process often remains fragmented. Nevertheless, individual educators, through personal initiative, strive to implement reading promotion and cultural programs that enhance learning and cultivate a love for books. Additionally, some school libraries organize book exhibitions, participate in national and European reading promotion programs, collaborate with local libraries and organizations, and support students' research projects. In some cases, where possible, they use digital tools and implement thematic educational activities, such as environmental and historical programs. They also organize reading and creative writing competitions, transforming the library into a lively centre for learning and culture. Yet, without structured institutional support, such efforts tend to remain fragmented and unsustainable over time, as noted in interviews.

In stark contrast to this reality, the 'Dimitris & Aliko Perrotis Library' of the American Farm School operates as a model learning commons, thanks to the foresight of its administration and targeted funding. As Damiana Koutsomicha (2025) clearly states: *'Our mission is to present a different kind of library model, a modern one. A learning environment that inspires students and teachers. It enhances teaching, research... with a vision... to empower it by laying the foundations for lifelong learning.'*

The result is a vibrant, participatory space where services are tailored to each educational level:

'In middle and high school we start laying the groundwork for how to structure a project, how to present it [...]. We talk about censorship, depending on the theme, and about copyright and plagiarism [...]. We also create escape rooms based on the archives [...] they search all over the campus [...]. it's experiential [...]. At the College... There are credit-bearing courses on topics like bibliography, information retrieval, presentations, the use of AI tools [...]. In the studio... a series of award-winning library podcasts were created... colleagues use the space as a learning tool...'

The Perrotis Library embodies the characteristics of a commons, as it has transformed, and continues to evolve, into an open, dynamic space for learning and collaboration. Its flexible layout, including a podcast studio, archive-based escape rooms, and multi-purpose learning areas, actively supports creativity and experiential education. Time in the library is no longer limited to silent study, but is reimagined through workshops, discussions on censorship and copyright, the use of AI tools, and student presentations. The school community actively participates in shaping content and activities, while services are tailored to different educational levels.

The Perrotis Library (Figure 2) proves that when a library transcends its traditional role, it can become a modern, open hub for learning and creativity, a model that can and should inspire the modernization of other school libraries.

Figure 2: Dimitris & Aiki Perrotis Library

Special/thematic Libraries

Special libraries in Greece operate within organizations, institutions, businesses, and agencies, serving a specialized audience with specific informational needs. They provide services such as cataloguing specialized materials, research support, access to specialized databases and archives, and technical assistance in information management. Most of these libraries belong to private entities and are adequately

funded, which allows some to provide excellent services and make a significant contribution to meeting the needs of their users.

2) Challenges

Although some Greek libraries have begun to adopt more modern and open practices, many of them still operate under traditional frameworks and face challenges that limit their contribution to education and learning. Insufficient funding remains one of the core barriers, restricting the renewal of collections, the development of technological infrastructure, and the provision of contemporary educational services. At the same time, the lack of specialized staff and limited opportunities for professional development make it difficult for libraries to support new learning models and digital skills. As Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025), Head of the University of Piraeus Library (Figure 3) noted: *‘We’ve tried to enhance learning support, but without stable staff development, it remains very limited in scope.’*

Figure 3: University of Piraeus Library

Progress in digital transformation is uneven, with many libraries lacking adequate technological equipment and access to modern online platforms. Spatial limitations, especially in older buildings, also hinder the creation of learning-conducive environments such as collaborative areas or quiet study zones. The digital divide further impacts equitable access to educational services, particularly for vulnerable groups such as the elderly, low-income individuals, and residents of remote areas. Likewise, gaps in accessibility and multilingual content limit the participation of people with disabilities and those from migrant backgrounds.

Innovation in libraries often remains fragmented, as it is usually based on short-term projects without long-term institutional support. According to Damiana Koutsomiha (2025), Head of the Dimitris & Aliko Perrotis Learning Commons at the American Farm School: *‘We try to introduce new models, but it’s difficult to sustain anything long-term without internal support and continuity.’*

The absence of a national strategic framework and weak interministerial coordination further restrict the ability of libraries to serve as key hubs for education, inclusion, and social cohesion.

3) Associated indicators

Policy Dimension

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries identified as actors for lifelong learning and education?	Yes	Law 3879/2010, titled ‘Development of Lifelong Learning and other provisions,’ establishes the National Network for Lifelong Learning in Greece ⁵ . This law recognizes various institutions as providers of lifelong learning, including libraries, thereby acknowledging their role in lifelong learning and education. Illustration: 21st-century skills workshops, p2p learning, and experiential learning.
Are libraries part of community development plans?	No	There is no explicit mention of libraries in national community development plans. While Law 3852/2010 (‘Kallikratis Programme’) reorganizes local government structures and responsibilities, it does not specifically designate libraries as actors in community development.
Are libraries included in OER/Open Science/Open Data policy?	Yes (at the institutional level)	Only academic libraries contribute via HEAL-Link, EKT, and institutional repositories. Several special and research centre libraries and a few innovative public libraries.

⁵ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/eurypedia/greece/legislation-and-official-policy-documents>

Do libraries cooperate with schools/universities nationally or internationally?	Yes	Greek academic libraries, through HEAL-Link, participate in national and international collaborations, including interlibrary loan services and shared digital resources ⁶ .
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Public and Educational Impact

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Number of people visiting public libraries per year	3,036,202 (2022)	According to the Hellenic Statistical Authority, this figure represents an 83.1% increase compared to 2020, indicating a significant rebound in library usage post-pandemic.
Number of students/teachers visiting university libraries per year	Unknown	While specific national data is unavailable, institutional records suggest high usage in active academic settings.
Academic libraries offering learning programs	Yes, in most universities (esp. large ones)	As of 2022, Greece had 167 libraries of legal entities, which include university libraries. Many of these institutions offer structured learning support programs, such as information literacy workshops and research assistance. Based on the 2023 data, 23 academic libraries in Greece offered learning or training programs ⁷ .
Public libraries offering learning programs	Yes	It depends on the initiative of the staff, the willingness to create and innovate and the funding. Almost all libraries offer educational programmes. But the issue is not just the offer. It needs

⁶ openaire.eu

⁷ https://mopab.seab.gr/sites/default/files/mopab_report_2023b_0.pdf

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		consistency, quality, progression, which is always lacking due to many factors.
School libraries offering learning programs	Rare, only in select private or well-funded public schools	Out of approximately 16,089 schools in Greece, only 499 have libraries, and many of these are not fully operational due to staffing and resource limitations. Consequently, structured learning support programs are rare in school libraries, with exceptions primarily in private institutions or specific public schools with dedicated funding.
Number of libraries for students	42 academic libraries + branches	As per HEAL-Link member institutions.
Number of libraries for citizens	347 public/municipal libraries	Based on the Hellenic Statistical Authority's 2022 survey, encompassing the National Library of Greece, 40 public libraries, and 139 municipal libraries.

<p>Are libraries working with NGOs, educational institutions, and associations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Many Greek libraries, particularly public and municipal, participate in collaborations with NGOs, educational institutions, and cultural bodies. Such collaborations are often project-based and rely heavily on EU or private funding. Eg. Future Library Initiative: Non-profit backed by the Stavros Niarchos Foundation; has collaborated with 167 libraries since 2011 on reading, creativity, and digital skills⁸. EXPLORAL Project: EU-funded program with the Library of Konitsa; focused on digital heritage and cross-border cultural exchange⁹. Eugenides Foundation Library: Privately funded; partners with the Hellenic Naval Academy and MarLiNet for training and maritime services¹⁰. City of Athens Library: Builds partnerships with local and international institutions to promote literature and culture¹¹.</p>
<p>User satisfaction related to the library</p>	<p>Partial</p>	<p>Some institutions conduct internal surveys, but there is no national benchmark for user satisfaction.</p>
<p>Number of cultural or civic events hosted per year</p>	<p>Unknown</p>	<p>While numerous activities are reported (e.g. exhibitions, community programs), data is not systematically collected at the national level.</p>

⁸ futurelibrary.gr

⁹ keep.eu

¹⁰ eef.edu.gr

¹¹ greeknewsagenda.gr

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b) Participation and Democratic Culture, including Social Inclusion and Equal Access

1) Overview

Libraries in Greece have the potential to become key contributors to democratic culture, social inclusion, and intercultural dialogue. Although there is no national policy framework that formally recognizes libraries as spaces for civic participation, the empowerment of marginalized groups, or intercultural engagement, beyond their traditional role as information and lending centres, some initiatives have already emerged that reflect an ongoing effort to gradually transform libraries into community-driven, participation-based environments.

Amidst this evolving landscape, The Open Library¹², founded and maintained by Giannis Farsaris, emerges as a grassroots model of digital transformation. Giannis Farsaris (2025), in his interview in the context of the LibCommons project, speaks about the Open Library, a project that exemplifies the notion of digital commons in action. It is a grassroots initiative focused on free access to knowledge, citizen participation, and democracy. The Open Library operates as a shared learning and cultural space, belonging to no one, but co-created by all... a living commons with no barriers, hierarchies, or gatekeeping. As he recalls, 'It all started back in 2009... just collecting and collecting...that's how the Open Library began.' Today, it contains over 14,000 digitized Greek books and 3,000 audio books, all freely accessible online. The initiative has no institutional backing. Instead, it relies entirely on a non-hierarchical, informal network of volunteers: 'The core group is about 30 people, but the broader network may reach 200.' The coordination is, as he describes, 'asteroid-like': 'I'm at the centre, and there are people who send me two or three books per week.' Access is fully inclusive and unrestricted. There is no content filtering or editorial gatekeeping, except for material with fascist or hate content: 'Our only red line is fascism. If a retired man writes poems full of spelling errors...so what? That's his voice, and it belongs here.'

One striking example of social inclusion is the unexpected success of a humble schoolbook: "Learn Greek," published in 1978 by the Sivitanidios Evening School', which became the year's most downloaded title. It was used by migrants preparing for Greek language exams. As Farsaris explains, '*You wouldn't believe it. It completely took off... so simple that someone who doesn't know Greek could still understand it.*' The Open Library is entirely self-funded by its creator: '*I quit smoking, and now I spend that money on hosting,*' he says. He has rejected funding offers from sponsors

¹² <https://www.openbook.gr/>

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attempting to impose conditions: *'I felt it was top-down, like they wanted to hijack the project. So, I walked away.'* The Open Library represents a contemporary model of digital commons: a shared resource that is created, maintained, and protected by its community. It offers a tangible example of how participation, inclusion, and access can become reality through voluntary collaboration and digital self-organization.

Some other libraries' efforts focus on accessibility. Assistive technologies such as Braille displays, screen readers, and tactile signage have been implemented in certain institutions (Antoniou et al., 2024), indicating a limited but growing sensitivity to inclusion. However, these technologies have not yet been widely adopted across national library systems. As of 2023, only 67% of Greek universities had established accessibility units, and fewer than half provided meaningful support for individuals with visual or hearing impairments (MoPAB, 2023). According to interviewees, such initiatives tend to be locally driven. Damiana Koutsomiha (2025), Head of the Perrotis College Library, notes: *'We're expected to be inclusive, but in many cases, there's no infrastructure or coordinated plan to make it possible.'*

A strong example is the Arcadia program implemented by the Perrotis Library, which supports students with learning difficulties or behavioural challenges through collaboration with special educators and psychologists: *'We've supported children with dyslexia, dysgraphia, behavioural issues... even children who just needed to feel accepted. One student, for instance, was integrated into our digitization team and felt valued.'*

Accessibility, however, is not limited to content, it also concerns infrastructure and equipment: *'Not all students have laptops or access to computers... So, one of our biggest efforts is to promote inclusion. Equal access for everyone.'*

The Library of the University of Patras, under the direction of Giannis Tsakonas, has extended its activities beyond its traditional academic role, taking on significant social initiatives. Through actions such as 'The Power of Words' (a creative writing program for students providing psychological support), the organization of a book-for-food exchange counter (where donated books are exchanged for food items distributed to vulnerable groups), participation in children's summer camps, and initiatives to help migrant communities create and preserve digital archives, the library demonstrates its active and tangible presence in the social sphere.

Giannis Tsakonas notes that the library, being the largest in the region, cannot ignore the local social context, especially in one of the country's most underdeveloped areas. While it does not claim the role of a 'saviour', the library places itself at the service of society with respect, discretion, and a strong focus on neutrality and long-term usefulness in its interventions. As he explains: *'What we saw, also from the personal*

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interest of some colleagues, was that we started working a bit with the community on a social level.’ One of the most illustrative examples was The Power of Words Initiative:

‘One of these initiatives was The Power of Words. It was an activity that emerged from discussions and the various stimuli we had. When we received the proposal from the Athens Comics Library to participate in this project... I think that became the framework for some of the ideas we already had. [...] We aimed to offer a kind of outlet, a way out and to the extent we could, we structured it properly. [...] We involved professionals, there was a psychologist in the program, and we regularly communicated with them. Each time there was a session, we discussed the topics students brought up. [...] Everything was done with the utmost discretion.’ (Tsakonas, 2025).

Local initiatives in 2021–2022 further showcased the creative and inclusive potential of libraries. The Athens Comics Library, in collaboration with the Refugee Week Greece¹³, a vibrant cultural festival celebrating the contribution, creativity and authenticity of people having experienced forced migration, implemented the ‘Library on Prescription’ program, using storytelling as a form of psychosocial support. This initiative created safe, expressive spaces for people facing mental health challenges, youth, individuals with learning disabilities, elderly women in remote villages, and incarcerated individuals, building community through a shared narrative.

In another case, the Feminist Library¹⁴ worked with MiQ and the local migrant community on the project ‘Anamesa/Ndërmjet,’ which engaged 20 second-generation queer migrants in participatory storytelling and visual expression, enabling them to craft their own narratives around migration and challenge dominant stereotypes.

Other special/thematic libraries adopted participatory decision-making approaches. In partnership with the Greek Forum of Migrants, some institutions invited community members to co-design library services. Migrants were treated not as passive recipients but as co-creators of library life, strengthening their sense of belonging and mutual support.

In school settings, new forms of collaboration emerged. Students, parents, and educators collectively reimagined their school libraries through open discussions, artwork, and group planning. Volunteers helped bring these visions to life by improving infrastructure, providing new equipment, and reinforcing the school community’s sense of ownership and care.

¹³ <https://refugeeweek.gr/about/>

¹⁴ <https://theuropechallenge.eu/building-safer-spaces-for-all/>

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At a time when national frameworks fall short, such local and institutional initiatives reveal the transformative power of libraries. As Koutsomicha (2025) powerfully states, *'Libraries are a creation of the society they serve... We shouldn't see them as churches. They are spaces where people come to connect, to express themselves, to be who they are.'*

Still, in Greece, such initiatives remain few and far between, and they often depend solely on the personal drive and vision of individual professionals or forward-thinking institutions.

2) Challenges

Despite notable initiatives, libraries in Greece have yet to develop a consistent role as institutions for social inclusion or civic engagement. Existing efforts remain fragmented and depend largely on the capacity and initiative of individual libraries in the absence of a unified national strategy. As noted by Anthi Katsirikou (2025), Head of the University of Athens Library and President of the Hellenic Association of Librarians and Information Scientists, *'We are trying to work on the "social" part, but this is essentially the university's responsibility and strategy.'*

Many public libraries, especially in rural or underfunded areas, struggle to meet even basic service needs, making it difficult to sustain inclusive programs (National Library of Greece, 2022). Accessibility is uneven, as assistive technologies (such as screen readers or adaptive workstations) are mainly available in better-resourced institutions (MoPAB, 2023).

Multilingual collections and services for migrants or refugees are also sporadic and often rely on NGO involvement rather than being structurally embedded in public institutions. Digital participation follows a similar pattern, with isolated pilot projects and little coordinated national support.

To fully realize their social and democratic potential, libraries need formal policy recognition, stable funding, and integration into national strategies for inclusion and citizen participation. Without these prerequisites, most efforts remain isolated, short-lived, and limited in impact.

3) Associated Indicators

While several Greek libraries implement meaningful practices that support social inclusion, civic engagement, and freedom of expression, these efforts tend to emerge from local initiatives or project-based funding rather than from a coherent national

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strategy. Libraries contribute to lifelong learning and accessibility through specific programs and infrastructure improvements. However, the lack of a national policy framework that explicitly positions libraries as stakeholders in democratic development limits their systemic impact. Furthermore, the absence of standardized indicators, such as tools for evaluating accessibility or mechanisms for tracking user participation in service design, makes it difficult to monitor progress or replicate successful models across the sector.

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries identified by the State as key actors to promote democratic culture?	No	There is no explicit national policy positioning libraries as civic or democratic actors. Their role in promoting democratic culture is mentioned indirectly through local or EU-funded initiatives.
Are libraries promoting freedom of expression?	Limited (documented in specific cases only)	There is no national policy or formal directive (e.g. through labels, official declarations, or structured actions). Positioning Greek libraries as promoters of freedom of expression (limits in collections, spaces, strategic plans, and accessibility).
Are libraries integrating the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Framework?	No systematic integration	There is currently no evidence of a coordinated effort or national strategy to integrate the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the services or programming of Greek libraries. Some fragmentary efforts by libraries and recently ANGLIS the Association of Greek Librarians and Information Scientists (AGLIS) has started to work on this. Veria Public Library, located in Northern Greece, sits at a confluence of numerous ethnic identities that are moving into the region. It offers immigrants from Albania, Russia, Ukraine and Bulgaria access to computers to create visual narratives about their lives. These stories are

		then posted on YouTube and on a dedicated project website. ¹⁵
Are there policies in favour of social inclusion and accessibility?	Limited; no comprehensive national policy	While Greek Higher Education Institutions are mandated by Law 4957/2022 to implement accessibility measures, public and municipal libraries lack a comprehensive national policy addressing social inclusion and accessibility. Some libraries have independently initiated inclusive programs, but these efforts are isolated and not part of a coordinated national strategy. Illustrations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Braille printers and accessible carrels at the American Farm School - Programs for children with learning difficulties with Arcadia program - Support services for the homeless at Veria Central Public Library
Is there a policy for people with disabilities or fewer opportunities?	Yes; established by law, but implementation is limited.	Accessibility policies exist at both national and institutional levels (e.g. Ministry of Culture). However, implementation remains uneven across libraries and regions. According to a national study (Samarakou, 2008), many libraries do not yet offer adequate accessible services, although progress has been made in certain institutions. The National Library of Greece has initiated accessible services and resources, but full compliance and coverage across the library network remain a work in progress.
Are users involved in service design?	No	With different, non-participatory methods/ways (e.g. users' surveys).

¹⁵ <https://www.eblida.org/Documents/EBLIDA-Report-SDGs-and-their-implementation-in-European-libraries.pdf>

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries supporting civic engagement or democratic learning?	Partial	There is no evidence of systematic or widespread engagement by Greek libraries in civic or democratic learning programs. Sporadic efforts are made mainly with funding from the European union such as the program ‘libraries prescription’ by the Athens comic Library.
Are digital skills and AI literacy included in training?	Partial	Many academic and public libraries in Greece (EKT, NTUA, University of Athens) support digital access and basic ICT use, but there is no evidence of structured training programs specifically focused on digital skills and no inclusion of AI literacy. From the interviews it emerges that the AFS library has started AI literacy programmes (Koutsomiha, personal communication, 2025).
Are inclusive programs provided for vulnerable populations?	Limited; with some notable initiatives	While some libraries ¹⁶ and academic institutions have introduced programs for vulnerable groups (refugees, minorities, and individuals with disabilities), such initiatives remain uneven. Accessibility Units exist in 67% of Greek universities; among these, 90% offer assistive technologies for visually impaired users and 50% for those with hearing impairments (MoPAB, 2023). While these examples demonstrate efforts to support vulnerable populations, such initiatives are relatively limited and not uniformly implemented across all Greek libraries. The majority of inclusive programs are concentrated in specific institutions or are driven by non-governmental organizations.

¹⁶ "Library Prescriptions – The Power of Words", University of Patras Library, We need books-Greece's first multilingual library and cultural center- <https://weneedbooks.org/> Arcadia program -AFS library -From interviews

c) Spatial Design and Shared Spaces

1) Overview

Efforts to improve spatial design in Greek libraries reflect a gradual and uneven process of adapting traditional infrastructures to contemporary educational, social, and accessibility needs. However, these transformations remain inconsistent and highly dependent on institutional priorities, building constraints, and external funding availability.

In academic libraries, some institutions have gradually experimented with redesigning physical spaces to support collaboration, digital learning, and user engagement. At the Perrotis College Library, for example, underutilized areas were repurposed into more flexible environments following internal needs assessments and administrative consultation. As Head Librarian Damiana Koutsomicha (2025) explains:

'In 2015, we saw our print reference section barely used. Inspired by US library models, we advocated for a flexible, student-centered environment. After presenting user data, pedagogical needs, and design examples to administrators and engineers, we repurposed the space into a vibrant learning commons.'

The redesigned space now hosts student group work, exhibitions and occasional community events. Its continued development, including plans to transform a fixed-seating amphitheatre into a modular classroom, reflects evolving learning needs, although these changes remain project-dependent.

Similarly, at the University of Piraeus, Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025) notes that physical constraints limited major layout changes, but local adaptations were still pursued: *'We added ergonomic furniture, smart lighting, and accessible workstations. While the building lacks layout flexibility, we prioritized inclusive infrastructure where possible.'*

These efforts demonstrate that even small-scale modifications can enhance inclusivity and adaptability in library spaces, though their success often hinges on a combination of institutional support and user involvement. This applies not only to academic settings but also to municipal libraries, where spatial innovation remains highly dependent on local leadership and targeted support.

In public libraries, spatial transformation faces greater challenges. While initiatives like the Stavros Niarchos Foundation's Future Library program (2011–2017), funded through private philanthropy, revitalized dozens of libraries with new layouts, technology corners, and children's areas, the long-term impact varies (Future Library,

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n.d.). Many municipal libraries, particularly those in smaller or under-resourced areas, continue to operate in rigid, aging buildings that limit physical adaptability. Moreover, participatory planning involving user communities remains the exception rather than the norm.

At the policy level, accessibility requirements are shaped by broader European directives (e.g. Directive 2019/882/EU) and initiatives like AccessibleEU. Yet implementation across Greek libraries is uneven, with no central mechanism for monitoring or enforcing spatial accessibility standards. The National Accessibility Authority exists, but library-specific oversight remains limited.

Notable spatial redesign efforts include the renovated Eugenides Foundation Library¹⁷ in Athens, which reopened to the public with expanded collaborative areas, upgraded technology infrastructure, and dedicated learning zones for students and researchers (News247, 2023). The Goethe-Institut Library in Athens¹⁸ has also modernized its layout, offering flexible workspaces, a curated digital collection, and a community-oriented reading room that supports intercultural exchange (Goethe-Institut, n.d.). In northern Greece, the Municipal Library of Kozani¹⁹ underwent a major transformation with EU structural funding, developing a modern, multifunctional space that serves both as a cultural venue and as a learning resource for the wider region (European Commission, 2023).

While impactful, these initiatives are primarily enabled by private foundations or EU-supported projects, rather than stemming from a coordinated national library infrastructure strategy. Their success underscores the uneven distribution of resources and the reliance on external funding for sustainable spatial development.

2) Challenges

In Greece, discussions about spatial design and shared spaces in libraries are gaining traction, but implementation remains limited and uneven. Only a few libraries have begun to reimagine their physical environments to support inclusion, collaboration, and civic engagement. However, these efforts are still isolated cases and have not yet become part of a broader, systemic shift.

One of the main challenges is infrastructure inequality. Libraries in smaller municipalities or older buildings often lack architectural flexibility and financial

¹⁷ Eugenides Foundation Library: <https://www.news247.gr/politismos/vivlia/anoigei-xana-gia-to-koino-i-vivliothiki-tou-idrimatos-evgenidou/>

¹⁸ Goethe-Institut Library, Athens: <https://www.goethe.de/ins/gr/el/sta/ath/bib.html>

¹⁹ Municipal Library of Kozani: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/el/projects/Greece/a-new-modern-library-for-kozani-greec

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resources needed to adopt inclusive spatial design. Features such as adjustable furniture, accessible entrances, or signage for users with disabilities are rare and usually dependent on project-based funding rather than integrated public investment. As Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025), Head of University of Piraeus Library and President of the Association of Greek librarians and information scientists (AGLIS) explains,

'The building itself is a challenge; we can't change the structure easily. So, we focused on smaller, strategic upgrades, like ergonomic chairs, smart lighting, and height-adjustable workstations. These changes were not costly, but they had a clear impact on how students used the space.'

Another major issue is the sustainability of innovation. While some libraries have created media labs, makerspaces, or podcast studios through short-term EU or private grants, these initiatives often fade once funding ends. The lack of long-term planning and national support mechanisms limits the ability of these spaces to become lasting elements of library services. Damiana Koutsomicha (2025), Head Librarian of the Perrotis College, illustrates the need for institutional backing:

'In 2015, we saw our print reference section barely used. Inspired by US models, we insisted on a student-centered redesign. We presented data and pedagogical needs, and the space became a vibrant learning commons. Still, developments like turning our amphitheatre into a modular classroom depend on new funding.'

There is also no cohesive national spatial policy linking library infrastructure to broader educational, cultural, or inclusion goals. Without a unified framework, spatial redesigns tend to be fragmented, relying on the motivation of individual staff members or local authorities rather than being part of a coordinated effort.

Furthermore, library staff are often not given the opportunity or support to participate in spatial innovation. Many lack formal training in ergonomics, accessibility, or user-centered space management, not due to unwillingness but because there is no institutional infrastructure to provide ongoing education or professional development in these areas. As a result, spatial projects often fall outside the expertise and capacity of existing teams.

User involvement in spatial design is also limited. While some libraries have piloted feedback collection mechanisms, the practice of co-design, particularly involving vulnerable or marginalized groups, has neither been institutionalized nor widely adopted. Participatory approaches remain largely unfamiliar within Greek library culture, and when they are implemented, they tend to occur indirectly or informally,

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lacking the structure and strategic planning necessary for meaningful user integration in the design process. As Koutsomicha (2025) notes,

'We use the space for student groups, exhibitions, and events, but what we lack is consistent programming support. It's not just about the room, it's what you do with it that matters. For instance, when users asked for screens, we installed them, but in the end, they weren't used. This shows that having the equipment is not enough; we need to think creatively about how to make use of these screens in ways that serve real needs and activate the space more meaningfully.'

Academic libraries have made efforts to enhance their physical environments, but the transformation remains partial. Although most Greek academic libraries have improved digital services and adopted elements of the 'information commons' model, they fall short of the fully collaborative environments envisioned in the 'Learning Commons' approach. Learning Commons are user-centered, flexible learning environments that integrate technology, services, and space design to promote collaboration, creativity, and active learning. They emphasize participatory governance and practical involvement of users in service delivery and space planning, fostering a shared responsibility between staff and community. According to Garoufali and Garoufallou (2022), while some libraries include writing centres or classrooms, facilities such as media labs, makerspaces, or visualization labs are rare. Moreover, most space-related changes over the past decade have focused on expanding shelving or updating furniture, rather than rethinking the learning environment itself. Staff recognize the need for transformation, but the shift in mindset and institutional vision necessary for a true Learning Commons have not yet occurred in a systematic way.

Finally, a growing concern is the underutilization and misalignment of designed spaces. Even when innovative areas like group learning zones or creative tech labs exist, they are often disconnected from the everyday functions of the library. Without trained staff, programmatic integration, or active community engagement strategies, these spaces risk becoming inactive rather than vibrant, inclusive environments.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries building inclusive spaces?	Yes (Partially)	Selected academic and public libraries (e.g. Veria Central Public Library, American Farm School, Chania Public Library) have implemented inclusive spatial features like modular layouts and accessibility accommodations. Practices remain project-based and not nationally standardized. <i>(Antoniou et al., 2024; Koutsomiha, 2025; Katsirikou, 2025; Tsakonas, 2025.)</i>
Are libraries creating places for minorities?	No clear data	Programs for refugees, children with learning differences, and intergenerational users are documented, but dedicated physical spaces or culturally specific design elements for minorities are not systematically recorded.
Are libraries accessible for people with disabilities?	Yes (Selectively)	Some libraries provide ramps, elevators, Braille printers, and adjustable furniture (e.g. American Farm School, Veria). However, accessibility remains inconsistent, especially in smaller or older buildings. <i>(MODIPAV Inclusion Guide; Koutsomiha, 2025; Katsirikou, 2025; Tsakonas, 2025.)</i>

How many hours are libraries open?	Varies by institution	Academic libraries generally follow university schedules (e.g. ~50–60 hours/week); public libraries operate typically 30–50 hours/week. No national benchmark published. <i>(Veria Public Library, n.d.; HEAL-Link members)</i>
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d) Digital Technologies and Information Access

1) Overview

In the digital era, access to information has emerged as a fundamental right and a key factor for equality, educational participation, lifelong learning, and social cohesion. Libraries, as traditional guardians of knowledge, are now called upon to adapt to a new environment in which information is primarily digital, globally available, and require digital literacy skills to be effectively utilized.

Digital technologies have the power to transform libraries by enhancing accessibility, diversity, and the dynamic nature of the information they offer. In Greece, this transition is not uniform but is progressing gradually, depending on the type of library, its geographic location, and the level of institutional or community support it receives.

Academic Libraries

University libraries in Greece are at the forefront of digital transformation. Through the national HEAL-Link network, they provide access to thousands of academic journals, e-books, and specialized databases. HEAL-Link also promotes Open Access, offering free availability of research results to the public. At the same time, academic libraries maintain institutional repositories for storing and sharing theses and dissertations and offer digital skills training programs for students and researchers. However, as Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025) of the University of Piraeus noted, ‘Much of what we do in digital services depends on motivated individuals; there’s no broader strategy guiding us.’

In this changing environment, Greek academic libraries are increasingly connected with European and international infrastructures. A notable example of this international engagement was highlighted during an interview with Dr. Giannis Tsakonas (2025), Director of the Library of the University of Patras and Vice President of LIBER, within

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the framework of the LibCommon program. His active participation in organizations such as LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries) and SCOSS (Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services) ensures the representation of the Greek library community in strategic international bodies. These organizations play a central role in promoting Open Science and ensuring the sustainability of non-commercial digital infrastructures, based on the principle of maintaining them as commons, common goods that belong to and serve the scientific and broader community. Within LIBER, specialized committees and working groups have been established, focusing on innovative scholarly communication, Open Access, copyright, citizen science, and educational resources.

Greek academic libraries have participated and continue to participate actively in these structures, with Giannis Tsakonas, serving as their representative and, at times, as coordinator of various working groups. The involvement of Greek libraries in these bodies, not only as members but also in leadership roles, reflects their significant contribution to shaping strategic policies at the European level and actively implementing them at the national level. However, despite their recognition and representation in international networks, the development of academic libraries within Greece often does not match this level of engagement. Institutional, financial, and political conditions do not equally support their alignment with international advancements, thus limiting the full utilization of the expertise and initiatives they bring back from abroad. Additionally, Tsakonas represents the Association in international bodies such as SCOSS, which coordinates funding for open science infrastructures. As he explained, SCOSS focuses not on content, but on infrastructures, and how these can remain open and autonomous, following the logic of commons. This means that infrastructures must have the financial capacity and autonomy to ensure their governance, management, and ownership, which should belong to the community under non-profit frameworks. Within this context, SCOSS supports major digital repositories and services, such as the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), and arXiv.

At the same time, Tsakonas participates in the governance of the Knowledge Rights 21 program, an international initiative promoting institutional and legislative changes in favour of openness in education, research, and innovation. The program is funded by the philanthropic organization Arcadia and implemented in collaboration with entities such as LIBER, IFLA, and SPARC Europe.

At the national level, the University of Patras Library has undertaken initiatives to strengthen Open Access. Beyond its involvement in research and funding programs, it conducts studies on the perceptions of the Greek academic community regarding open access, with a recent example being a survey that gathered 1400 responses

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from across the country. Furthermore, it monitors international indicators such as the Open Science Monitoring to align national policies with European directions.

Thus, academic libraries in Greece no longer limit themselves to providing access to scientific content but are gradually transforming into vibrant hubs of open knowledge production and dissemination. Aligned with the principles of equality, sustainability, and international cooperation, they consistently move towards the logic of commons, knowledge as a common good that belongs to and serves society. Through their participation in national and international networks, strengthening open science, and supporting corresponding infrastructures and policies, these libraries strive, step by step, to create conditions for more collective, fair, and sustainable access to knowledge, placing it at the core of the public sphere and collective benefit.

National Library of Greece (NLG)

The National Library is following a gradual path toward strengthening its digital presence. Through its digital platform, it provides access to a significant number of digitized materials such as manuscripts, newspapers, maps, and rare books. Some titles are also available for online reading. The NLG participates in European networks like Europeana, uses modern management technologies (such as RFID), and implements digital literacy programs for students, teachers, and the public.

Public and Municipal Libraries

Public and municipal libraries show significant variation in their level of digital integration. Some, like the Veria Central Public Library, stand out for their innovation: they offer MakerSpaces, robotics labs, digital storytelling programs (such as *Medusa*), and creative learning services using digital tools. However, in many smaller or remote areas, serious deficiencies persist. Some libraries lack even basic computer access for users. This geographic disparity limits universal access to modern forms of information and services.

School Libraries

School libraries present both significant potential and serious challenges. In most cases, a lack of infrastructure restricts the use of digital technologies. Nevertheless, some schools, especially through participation in European programs (like eTwinning or Erasmus+), enhance their use of platforms such as e-class and e-me for integrating the library into the learning process. With proper support, school libraries can play a crucial role in developing digital skills from an early age.

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Research/Thematic Libraries

Libraries affiliated with research centres, museums, or specialized institutions, such as the National Documentation Centre (EKT), are distinguished by their advanced use of digital technologies. They manage specialized collections, maintain thematic repositories, and offer digital services that support research. These libraries apply metadata standards, promote Open Access, and use digital preservation tools, contributing significantly to both national and international scientific communities.

Access to information is a pillar of education, scientific progress, and active citizenship in the knowledge society. Digital technologies offer enormous opportunities to expand this access, but their implementation in Greek libraries depends on institutional support, technical infrastructure, and human resources.

Although there are significant efforts in certain library sectors and exemplary cases, such as the National Library, there are still major inequalities, both thematic and geographic. Enhancing technological infrastructure and promoting digital literacy for all citizens must become a national priority so that libraries can continue to serve as hubs of knowledge, innovation, and equitable access to information.

2) Challenges

Despite notable efforts toward digital modernization, Greek libraries continue to face substantial and uneven challenges in the equitable integration of technology. In many public libraries, especially in rural or economically disadvantaged regions such as Grevena, Karditsa, or parts of the Dodecanese islands in the Aegean Sea, digital infrastructure remains insufficient. According to Koutsomicha (2025), *'We had this podcast corner set up with external support... but over time, it didn't really get used because we didn't have the right people to keep it going.'*

This underscores how innovation without staff capacity or integration quickly becomes unsustainable.

Reports such as the Knowledge Rights 21 country report (2025) highlight that most public libraries in Greece still lack legal access to licensed e-books and databases, offering only digitized public domain content. The National Library of Greece stands as one of the few exceptions.

Project-based initiatives, such as the Future Library²⁰ program funded by the Stavros Niarchos Foundation and Google, introduced digital innovations like podcast studios

²⁰ <https://futurelibrary.gr/>

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and makerspaces in selected libraries. However, without institutional integration or long-term funding, many of these spaces have not endured. Yet many of these innovations were not structurally embedded, and their longevity depended on short-term funding cycles.

A significant issue remains the shortage of trained personnel. Most public libraries lack staff with digital competencies in areas such as data literacy, media production, or digital citizenship education. According to the *Guide to the Educational Role of Libraries* (MODIPAV²¹, 2024), continuous professional development in digital skills remains *'uneven, and in many cases, absent'*.

In academic libraries, national bodies like HEAL-Link and the National Documentation Centre (EKT) have supported the development of open-access repositories and research data infrastructures. However, these resources are largely confined to university environments, and digital services, even within academia, tend to depend on department-level initiative rather than coordinated policy (Papadimitriou, 2021; OpenAIRE²², n.d.; EKT, n.d.).

Users also face persistent barriers. Digital literacy is unevenly addressed, leaving older adults, migrants, and low-income users without adequate support. While some libraries like those in Veria and Chania offer ICT workshops for these groups, scale remains limited.

Furthermore, the lack of curricular integration of digital education within libraries restricts sustained outreach, especially in public settings without stable staffing. Though private institutions like the American Farm School have developed advanced media literacy and misinformation workshops, these models are not easily replicated in municipal libraries due to funding and staffing constraints.

Finally, Greece lacks a cohesive national strategy for the digital transformation of libraries. The absence of a central coordinating body or shared framework for technological upgrades, training, and content access has led to duplication, inefficiencies, and stagnation. While Greece aligns with European directives on open science in principle, its public-facing library infrastructure lacks the policy mechanisms and financial support required for broad implementation (EKT, n.d.; OpenAIRE, n.d.).

Without structural support, many promising digital initiatives risk remaining isolated pilot efforts. For libraries to function as equitable and sustainable digital access points

²¹ <https://mopab.seab.gr/?q=en>

²² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

in Greek society, a systemic approach is needed, combining national governance, ongoing investment, professional capacity building, and inclusive user engagement.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Do libraries have a role in digital skills and literacy?	Yes	Libraries are increasingly engaging in digital skills education, though implementation is inconsistent and typically project based. -AI and digital tools training -Digital citizenship for primary school students -Media literacy and misinformation detection

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
% of electronic vs physical books	Low (~9%)	In 2023, 1,018 electronic book titles were published in Greece compared to 11,165 print titles, meaning e-books accounted for approximately 9% of total book production. Despite growth during the COVID-19 pandemic, e-book output remains limited and highly concentrated among a few large publishers. <i>Source: BookPoint database, accessed Dec. 2024; OSDEL (2023), 'Greek Book Production and Publishing Activity 2009–2022.'</i>
Availability of institutional repositories	Yes	Institutional repositories are presented in most Greek universities and supported by HEAL-Link, OpenAIRE, and the National Documentation Centre (EKT). These platforms facilitate open access to scholarly content and research data.

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<p>Availability of open-access educational/research material</p>	<p>Partial</p>	<p>While there are significant efforts and infrastructures in place to support open access in Greece, the availability of such materials varies across institutions and disciplines. Notably, the Kallipos project provides open-access academic textbooks for higher education and constitutes a key national infrastructure in this field (Kallipos.gr). HEAL-Link, the national consortium of academic libraries, has also promoted open access through agreements with major publishers, allowing researchers to publish without article processing charges, though institutional repository use remains limited. The National Documentation Centre (EKT) hosts platforms like <i>OpenArchives.gr</i> and <i>SearchCulture.gr</i>, offering wide access to scientific and cultural material, including over 44,000 doctoral dissertations. Despite such initiatives, awareness and integration of Open Educational Resources (OER) and governmental open data into teaching and research practices remain uneven.</p>
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Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
<p>Number of workshops/training sessions for digital literacy</p>	<p>No national data</p>	<p>Confirmed through interviews and local websites (e.g. Veria, Chania), but no centralized registry or national reporting mechanism.</p>
<p>Number of people accessing these workshops</p>	<p>No national data</p>	<p>Individual libraries estimate hundreds of participants per year, but data is institution-specific and not standardized.</p>

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
<p>% of access to digital collection</p>	<p>Partial (~20 – 30% in public libraries; ~70–90% in academic libraries)</p>	<p>Academic & Research Libraries</p> <p>HEAL-Link represents all 43 Greek universities and many research centres, providing access to tens of thousands of electronic resources. Through consortium agreements, HEAL-Link covers around 27,000 journal titles and 139,000 e-books, serving nearly the entire higher education sector.^{23 24}</p> <p>Open Access agreements (e.g. with Wiley, Elsevier, ACS) allow corresponding authors at participating institutions to publish OA without APCs, with coverage extended to 42+ institutions as of mid-2024²⁵</p> <p>A 2022 survey by the HEAL-Link Scholarly Communication Unit reported that while OA publishing support is active, less than one third (≈30 %) of Greek researchers regularly deposit work in institutional repositories.</p> <p>Public & Municipal Libraries</p> <p>There is no centralized monitoring, but available data suggests limited digital access. According to ELSTAT (2023), only 9.3 % of library users accessed electronic databases. A 2025 Knowledge Rights 21 report confirms that most public libraries lack licensed e-books, offering only digitized public-domain content, indicating digitization capabilities in fewer than 20–30 % of institutions.</p>

²³ https://wos.fecyt.es/news/2007/ponencias_seminario_ccre/HEAL-Link-Claudine_Xenidou.pdf

²⁴ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Academic-libraries-and-OA-books-in-Europe-overview-web-version.pdf>

²⁵ <https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/affiliation-policies-payments/heal-link-agreement.html>

		<p>Cultural Institutions & National Archives</p> <p>Platforms like Europeana/Greece have digitized over 500,000 Greek cultural objects, a significant, yet partial, representation of the country's total heritage.²⁶</p> <p>The National Library of Greece includes digitized manuscripts, newspapers, and maps on its online platform, though published usage stats are uncommon.</p>
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²⁶ <https://www.ekt.gr/en/news/22416>

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<p>% of open access collection</p>	<p>High in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) Estimated range: ~50–60% of academic output in Greece is available through open access.</p>	<p>According to the National Documentation Centre (EKT), over 52.8% of scholarly publications from Greek institutions between 2006 and 2020 were open access (EKT, 2023).</p> <p>HEAL-Link has established transformative agreements with publishers such as Springer Nature, Wiley, and Elsevier, enabling APC-free publishing for affiliated authors (HEAL-Link, 2022).</p> <p>Platforms like OpenArchives.gr and SearchCulture.gr aggregate hundreds of thousands of OA items, including theses, articles, and cultural content (EKT, n.d.).</p> <p>However, HEAL-Link’s Scholarly Communication Unit (2022) reports that only ~30% of researchers regularly deposit their work in institutional repositories, suggesting underutilization of green OA channels.</p>
<p>Number of open datasets</p>	<p>Unknown</p>	<p>Available evidence from the Knowledge Rights 21 report indicates that digital lending services (e-books, databases) remain very limited in most municipal libraries, aside from a few pilot cases and the National Library, mainly due to funding, staffing, and licensing constraints. No centralized data exist on what percentage of municipal libraries have digitization capabilities.</p>

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<p>Number of Open Educational Resources (OER)</p>	<p>Unknown (At least ~9,000–10,000 confirmed OER units, with additional materials scattered in platforms like Open eClass and institutional repositories).</p>	<p>While Greece hosts several OER platforms, including Kallipos (with 1,600+ open textbooks) and Photodentro (7,000+ K-12 digital resources), there is no centralized tracking of the total number of OERs produced or curated by libraries. University platforms like Open eClass and institutional repositories contain additional OERs, but access varies, and many are not publicly indexed.</p>
<p>% of open-source software used</p>	<p>Partially Available</p>	<p>While there is no systematic national monitoring of open-source software (OSS) use in Greek libraries, existing case studies and sectoral surveys suggest moderate but uneven adoption. A 2020 survey by EA/AAK (Open Technologies Alliance) involving 120 public and educational institutions estimated OSS usage at approximately 22%, primarily for systems such as Koha (library cataloguing) and DSpace or EPrints (institutional repositories), particularly in academic settings. Research centres like FORTH also rely on OSS-based infrastructures, including Linux-based HPC systems.</p> <p>In the private sector, Eurostat (2022) estimates OSS use below 20%, with slightly higher rates in tech startups. Overall, Greece ranks below the EU average in OSS adoption, reflecting a lack of national strategy</p>

		despite strong local initiatives (ΕΛ/ΛΑΚ, 2020; EU Open-Source Policy Report, 2021).
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Greek libraries are engaged in digital skills promotion and open access expansion, particularly in higher education institutions. However, the absence of national data collection frameworks limits the ability to measure the scale and reach of digital literacy programming, usage of OER, or adoption of open technologies across the sector.

3. Conclusion

The current landscape of libraries in Greece reveals a sector characterized by significant potential yet constrained by enduring structural limitations. Despite isolated efforts toward modernization and the adoption of open practices, chronic underfunding, insufficient professional development, limited digital infrastructure, and the absence of a coherent national strategic framework continue to impede libraries' ability to serve as integral components of the educational ecosystem.

As emphasized in recent interviews, sustained institutional change remains elusive without internal support, stable staffing, and long-term planning. Importantly, Dr. Anthi Katsirikou (2025), underscores the necessity of inter-library collaboration, arguing that no library can operate effectively in isolation. Participation in national and international networks such as HEAL-Link, the Hellenic Economic Library Network, IFLA, and thematic consortia have proven essential for knowledge exchange, access to shared infrastructure, and professional capacity building.

To address spatial, technological, and service disparities, particularly in underserved or remote areas, Katsirikou (2025) advocates for a regional mapping of libraries to identify opportunities for complementarity and strategic partnerships. This includes collaborations with schools and the development of domain-specific library networks (e.g. health information services) that could support both centralized institutions and peripheral community facilities.

In sum, the advancement of Greek libraries as inclusive, knowledge-driven institutions demands a coordinated national strategy, cross-sectoral policy alignment, investment in human and technological resources, and a firm commitment to inter-institutional collaboration. Only through such a systemic and sustained approach can libraries fulfil their transformative role in education, digital inclusion, and social cohesion.

4. SWOT Analysis

Theme	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Role of Libraries in Learning and Education	<p>Strong academic library infrastructure and services (HEAL-Link, Open Access, repositories).</p> <p>Participation in national and international networks (OpenAIRE, LIBER).</p> <p>Educational initiatives: MOOCs, information literacy programs, digital skills workshops.</p> <p>Model examples such as Perrotis Library and the University of Patras Library.</p>	<p>Chronic understaffing, especially in public and academic libraries.</p> <p>Absence of a national strategy recognizing libraries as educational institutions.</p> <p>Significant disparities in service quality and accessibility across library types and regions.</p> <p>Limited integration of certified educational programs into schools and public libraries.</p>	<p>Integration of libraries into lifelong learning and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) strategies.</p> <p>Strengthening collaborations with schools, universities, and NGOs.</p> <p>Development of a national platform for library-based learning and digital education.</p>	<p>Dependency on external or temporary funding sources.</p> <p>Institutional neglect and lack of long-term planning.</p> <p>Loss of expertise due to retirements without replacement.</p>

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<p>Participation and Democratic Culture, Social Inclusion and Equal Access</p>	<p>Initiatives supporting vulnerable groups (e.g. refugees, LGBTQ+, and people with disabilities).</p> <p>Libraries as spaces for civic expression and community-based programs.</p> <p>Strong local partnerships with NGOs and community stakeholders.</p>	<p>No national framework for civic engagement through libraries.</p> <p>Uneven implementation of accessibility technologies and inclusive services.</p> <p>Limited multilingual and intercultural content and programming.</p> <p>Lack of impact data and absence of standardized indicators to measure participation, inclusion, and community engagement.</p>	<p>Formal policy recognition of libraries in democratic education agendas.</p> <p>Access to EU funding for civic and community participation initiatives.</p> <p>Development of user engagement metrics and participatory service design.</p>	<p>Social exclusion if inclusion efforts remain fragmented and under-resourced.</p> <p>Over Reliance on personal initiative rather than systemic support.</p>
<p>Spatial Design and Shared Spaces</p>	<p>Redesign of spaces into learning commons and collaborative zones (e.g. Perrotis, Kozani).</p> <p>Implementation of accessibility-focused features (ergonomic furniture, lighting, ramps).</p> <p>Participation in international and national spatial</p>	<p>Inequality in infrastructure, especially in rural, municipal, or school libraries.</p> <p>Lack of staff training in space planning, accessibility, and co-design practices.</p> <p>Minimal participatory planning with user communities.</p>	<p>Establishment of national guidelines for inclusive, flexible, and co-designed library spaces.</p> <p>Leveraging EU and foundation funding for physical upgrades.</p> <p>Partnerships with architecture/design schools for spatial innovation.</p>	<p>Risk of abandoned or underused spaces due to lack of continuity or integration.</p> <p>Innovation fatigue in libraries without institutional and financial backing.</p>

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	innovation projects.			
Digital Technologies and Information Access	Strong digital presence of academic libraries through HEAL-Link, repositories, and Open Access.	Digital divide between institutions (public vs. academic, urban vs. rural).	Develop a national strategy for digital libraries and technology integration.	Technological exclusion of older adults, migrants, and low-income users.
	Use of advanced tools in selected libraries (e.g. makerspaces, podcast labs, AI training).	Absence of a national digital transformation strategy for libraries.	Expand the use of Open Educational Resources (OER), digital platforms, and AI tools.	Risk of obsolescence without long-term investment in infrastructure and staff development.
	Active participation in international networks promoting open science and digital inclusion.	Lack of staff with adequate digital competencies and minimal structured training.	Collaborate with organizations like EKT, HEAL-Link, and Open Technologies Alliance (ELLAK).	Termination of EU-funded digital innovation projects without state follow-up.

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Case: SPAIN

1. General context

The IFLA-UNESCO Public Library Manifesto (p. 1), updated in 2022, states that public libraries are ‘a living force for education, culture, inclusion and information’, as well as ‘an essential agent for sustainable development and for individual fulfilment of peace and spiritual welfare through the minds of all individuals’.

Taking into account this definition and the function of public libraries, this research is focused on the analysis of the content of national and regional documents in order to define the strategic role of libraries. At the same time, an analysis of libraries in the immediate area was carried out based on interviews with professionals linked to the Municipal Library Network of the Province of Barcelona (Xarxa de Biblioteques Municipals de la Província de Barcelona, XBMB), and libraries from the University of Vic and from the city of Vic. These interviews were complemented by 3 other international experts. The total number of professionals interviewed from Catalonia, Portugal and Colombia was 12:

- Núria and Txell – Library technicians at the Biblioteca del Montseny de Vic.
- Ignasi Janer – General coordinator of the Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés in Vic.
- Gemma Mascaró – Director – and Montse Aguilar – Coordinator of the User Services Area of the Biblioteca Miramarges, University of Vic.
- Trini Molist and Albert Rivas – Library technicians of the Library of Things Network of Vic (Xarxa de les Biblioteques de les Coses de Vic).
- Marta Cano – Barcelona County Libraries network general manager, Enric Vilagrosa – Head of the Planning, Evaluation and Quality section, and Andreu Orte – Head of the XBMB.
- Nico Barbieri – Researcher in the field of cultural rights (Barcelona).
- Natalia Duque Cardona – Associate Professor at the University of Antioquia (Medellín, Colombia).
- Sandra Zuluaga – Director of Fundación Ratón Biblioteca (Medellín, Colombia).
- Tatiana Sanches – Head of the Library of the Faculty of Psychology and Education at the University of Lisbon.

The aim was to identify and analyse the existing library services in order to corroborate whether the libraries of the XBMB are in line with the objectives of the aforementioned IFLA-UNESCO Public Library Manifesto.

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The current landscape of Catalan Libraries

Catalonia is a region located in the north-east of Spain with a population of 8 million inhabitants. Catalonia has its own culture and language (Catalan) and consolidated political institutions. It possesses competences in areas such as education, culture, and public services. Economically, Catalonia is one of the most dynamic regions in Southern Europe (European Commission, 2022²⁷), with a strong industrial base, a well-developed service sector, and a growing knowledge economy. Socially, it is a diverse territory with an important urban concentration around Barcelona that acts as a cultural, economic and technological hub for the region. Almost 6 million people live around it, while the rest of the territory is home to the other 2 million, with many rural areas that, like many other areas in Europe, are losing population and are in danger of being abandoned. Although Catalonia has made a commitment to social cohesion, public infrastructure and innovation, it also faces challenges such as inequalities in access to services, demographic changes and political tensions linked to the debate on self-determination. In this context, public libraries play a key role as spaces for universal access to knowledge, cultural participation and community cohesion.

The libraries analysed in Catalonia are part of the Public Library Network of the Diputació de Barcelona (Xarxa de Biblioteques Municipals de la Diputació de Barcelona, XBM). Diputacions are supra-municipal local bodies that provide technical, financial and legal support to municipalities. There are four of them in Catalonia, corresponding to its four provinces: Barcelona, Tarragona, Girona and Lleida. The Diputació de Barcelona, with a budget of 1.243.78 M € for 2024, is the largest of the four (Diputació de Barcelona, 2024²⁸). In the province of Barcelona, it is the Library Services Management (Gerència de Serveis de Biblioteques de la Diputació de Barcelona) which manages, assesses and supports the local councils in the creation and development of library services. It also leads the Municipal Library Network of the Province of Barcelona (XBMB) in order to guarantee territorial balance and quality of service in library matters, as well as the access of all citizens to information, knowledge and culture.

The Library Services Management has central services and operates throughout the Barcelona Province via the Municipal Library Network. A team of professionals from different backgrounds works daily from the Management Office to provide technical assistance and specialized advice necessary to obtain quality libraries available to all the municipalities in the province, from the smallest to the largest. The Municipal

²⁷ European Commission (2022). European Regional Competitiveness Index (RCI). Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy.

²⁸ <https://www.diba.cat/en/web/sala-de-premsa/-/la-diputacio-de-barcelona-aprova-un-pressupost-de-1.243-78-milions-d-euros-al-servei-de-les-persones-i-del-territori?>

Library Network is divided into twelve zones (eleven of supra-municipal scope and one specifically for the city of Barcelona). Each zone has a central library, whose director also serves as the head of the zone and acts as a key contact and representative of the Library Services Management in the area.

Public libraries

Date	2022	2023	2024
Libraries	233	233	235
Mobile libraries (rural)	10	12	12
Total number of libraries and mobile libraries	243	245	247

As of 2024, there are **235** libraries in the province of Barcelona, along with 12 mobile libraries (bibliobusos), which will be explained in more detail below.

% of people visiting a library each year

Date	2022	2023	2024
Users			
Registered users (TOTAL)	2.236.022	2.199.017	2.093.487
Registered users (women)	1.258.963	1.237.553	1.199.240
Registered users (men)	927.829	903.111	856.906
Registered users (unspecified)	49.230	58.353	37.341

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New user registrations	168.639	189.890	192.117
New user registrations (women)	87.218	99.945	100.129
New user registrations (men)	66.717	77.230	78.356
New user registrations (unspecified)	10.016	12.715	13.632

Visits 13.503.998 16.676.215 17.315.097

Amount of money invested in libraries

124,863,766.48 euros. It is worth noting that current expenditure has been increasing year after year since 2020. Of the nearly 125 million euros, just under 40% is funded by the Diputació de Barcelona, while local councils contribute slightly less than 60%, and the Generalitat (Government of Catalonia) provides nearly 3%.

Academic libraries

The 8 main university libraries in the province of Barcelona are the following: Universitat de Barcelona (University of Barcelona), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Universitat Ramon Llull, Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Universitat Abat Oliba, and Universitat de Vic – Universitat Central de Catalunya.

Number of people that work in libraries (public/academic)

Date	2022	2023	2024
Library staff	1.475	1.491	1.505
Mobile library staff	20	22	22
Total staff	1.495	1.513	1.527
Total staff (women)	1.146	1.184	1.172

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Total staff (men)	349	329	355
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Of these 1505 people working there in 2024, approximately 500 are part of XBM and around 1000 are librarians from the municipal councils of the province of Barcelona.

Key educational or cultural programs

The libraries of the Diputació de Barcelona are not just places for reading and consultation, but true cultural and educational laboratories at the service of the community. Through innovative, creative and locally-based programmes, libraries become active agents of social transformation, promoting participation, equity and lifelong learning. The following programmes illustrate how libraries can address topics as diverse as reading, citizen science, music, health, cinema or gender equality, all generating links between institutions, local authorities and citizens.

A) **Laboratori de lletres i imatges** (Laboratory of books and images). Biblioteca Roca Umbert (Granollers). A creative space that invites families to experiment with reading, understood in the broadest sense of the word: reading with all their senses, reading images and sounds, literary creation as a game, poetic imagination as an artistic form. The aim is to broaden families' reading references and enrich their reading itinerary and also to create special, emotional and experiential encounters around reading and books that will remain in children's memories

B) **Instant musicals** (Musical moments). Biblioteca Ca l'Oliveres (Lliçà d'Amunt) Twenty-minute musical auditions in the Music, Image and Magazines Area of the library. They are carried out by students from the local Music School and are open to all audiences. The auditions coincide with other organized activities. The aim is to offer a different and dynamic vision of the space, attracting new audiences and fostering collaboration with local organizations.

C) **Escriure de cinema**. (Writing about cinema.) It is a pilot scheme of the XBM in collaboration with Escola La Casa del Cine that proposes new participatory experiences in a film criticism workshop.

D) **De l'hort a la biblioteca** (From the garden to the library). A project that aims to get to know the local produce of the agricultural park, Parc Agrari del Baix Llobregat, and to get closer to a healthier lifestyle and diet. It aims to help to cultivate urban gardens and teach the best recipes for the products that you will obtain.

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E) **Bibliolab Ciència – Ciutat Saludable** (Science Library Lab – Healthy City, Different libraries from Barcelona). Involvement of citizens in the generation of knowledge to address the improvement of mobility in the city of Barcelona and its quality of life through science. Citizen science projects. Workshops on the co-creation of healthy cities.

F) **TecnoGirl**. Biblioteques del Maresme. Fundació Tecnocampus Mataró – Maresme. Awareness-raising: exhibition on scientific and technological women linked to the city of Mataró. Knowledge and action: intensive and practical workshops on science and technology. HackGirl junior: to promote technological vocations in the group of girls aged between 12 and 18 years and with the social challenge of waste management.

G) **La Biblioteca Humana** (The Human Library). Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés (Vic). An initiative born in Denmark in 2000 and now present in more than 80 countries, it promotes tolerance and understanding between different people. In these safe spaces for dialogue, open conversations are established between ‘Books’ (people with experiences often labelled by society) and small groups of ‘Readers’. The aim is to break down prejudices through active and personal listening, under the slogan *Unjudge someone*.

Key Actions for the Public With Disabilities or With Fewer Opportunities

Public libraries play a fundamental role in building a more inclusive and equitable society. Through initiatives aimed at people with disabilities, vulnerable groups or those with fewer opportunities, libraries provide spaces for meetings, empowerment and universal access to knowledge. The projects presented below show how, through proximity and social innovation, libraries can foster cohesion, autonomy and active participation of all citizens, especially those groups that are often underrepresented in the cultural and educational sphere:

A) **Aprenem** (Let’s learn). Biblioteca Mestre Martí Tauler (Rubí) i Biblioteca Marc de Vilalba (Cardedeu). The Aprenem workshops are based on language exchange and participation is free of charge. The aim is to facilitate language learning through practical groups and conversation workshops, without stressing grammar. It improves lifelong learning and facilitates inclusive and collaborative education.

B) **Xpresa’t** (Express yourself). Biblioteca Mestre Martí i Tauler (Rubí). Activity for young people aged 14 and over aimed at sharing their knowledge or skills. Proposals for activities that come from the youth themselves and that they share with other young people. Increasing the bank of knowledge. Integration of specific groups of young people with weak community ties, encouraging greater

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involvement and participation. Responding to young people with different needs so that they feel the library as their own.

C) **Cuchara Associació d'emancipació alimentària**. Open kitchen in Santa Coloma, at the Biblioteca del Fondo (Santa Coloma de Gramenet). It is a participatory space for community learning about food as a tool for health and sustainability. The project is based on the Cuines del Món (World Cuisines) project of the Biblioteca del Fondo and evolves towards social innovation. Its aim is to create and foster an inclusive, community-oriented space for coexistence and exchange through gastronomy and food.

D) **Biblioteca i centres educatius de justícia juvenil** (Library and educational centres of juvenile justice), Libraries of the Diputació de Barcelona. Promotion of the creation of inclusive projects based on culture and reading as a way of social integration and insertion. The objectives of this project are to make public reading available to groups with special needs, in this case to young people in juvenile justice centres; to work on culture and reading as a tool for social integration and reintegration, and to establish ways of collaboration, both at the supra-municipal and local level, with juvenile justice centres. The methodology has been based on mutual knowledge and the definition of the project through meetings between the agents involved.

E) **Biblioteca Bon Pastor**. At this library in Barcelona, volunteer positions were opened for young people with Autism Spectrum Disorder to carry out voluntary work providing technical support to the library.

F) **Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés de Vic**. This library in the city of Vic has functional adaptation programmes for people with blindness (marked floors, information in Braille). For people with visual impairments, iconography is prioritized over text, and the library entrance features a ramp ensuring physical accessibility for everyone. Additionally, the library lends its laboratory space to the local deaf association to translate the monthly activities into sign language and project them on the entrance hall screens.

Key Takeaway

In 2024, in the province of Barcelona, there was an increase in the number of registered visits and attendees at activities, although these figures did not surpass pre-Covid-19 levels. There was a significant increase in book lending services, exceeding the pre-crisis records by a considerable margin. Meanwhile, Internet-related services (Wi-Fi and Internet) showed stagnation -or even decline – interlibrary loan transactions continued to grow, increasing at a relatively higher rate than standard lending.

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In 2024 the XBM expanded with the addition of two new libraries (one in Sant Julià de Vilatorrada and another in Palau-Solità i Plegamans), which resulted in an increase of nearly 3,000 square metres in usable library service space. At the end of 2024, there were just over 2 million registered users, of which over 800,000 (39%) were registered as active. This percentage has been gradually rising following changes in the user deactivation policy, although the proportion of active users in relation to the total population has remained stable at around 14%. In general, library services are used more frequently by women than by men, although this varies depending on the specific service.

2. Case analysis

a) Role of Libraries in Learning and Education

1) Overview

Through the different interviews carried out, both with library professionals from Catalonia and from Colombia and Portugal (contrast), it can be said that, on a general level, public libraries are taking on an increasingly important role in the processes of lifelong learning and education and are at a key moment of redefinition and reorientation of their educational role in society. This is a key element that we want to highlight, and which is linked to the relevance of the LibCommon project: the richness of the debates, pilot schemes, and new initiatives currently being explored by libraries – particularly public libraries in Spain, but also, to a lesser extent, university libraries. In the transition from being merely repositories of books to becoming educational, contextual and community-based spaces that promote active citizenship and participation, many new and diverse paths are being explored – both conceptually and in practice. We hope that the LibCommon project can contribute to guiding this transition towards libraries becoming ‘lively infrastructures’ (Amin, 2014), ‘social infrastructures’ (Collet and Ball, 2024) in each territory – key spaces for participatory, community-led, and democratic development.

As we say, in this transition, on the one hand, they continue to maintain classic library services: books, CDs, DVDs and table games loans, access to digital and technological resources such as computers or free Internet connections and access to study and work rooms. On the other hand, they have new functions linked to different cultural activities, such as reading clubs, workshops on digital literacy, cinema, writing and video games, as well as workshops and a variety of family activities.

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As in the field of formal education, Finland has also become a reference in the field of non-formal education, especially for the public libraries of the city of Vic, which have taken the libraries of the city of Helsinki as a point of reference. This is the case of Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés, a meeting point focused on people, beyond reading. Its multidisciplinary team, made up of educators, cultural facilitators, etc., plays an important social role, welcoming children and young people who are unable to take part in extracurricular activities due to a lack of resources. They also take in homeless people. This social and community-oriented role is shared by the Biblioteca del Montseny, also in the city of Vic. Here, it is the Neighbourhood Association that uses the space to help new children with few cultural and economic resources, helping them to learn Catalan and to do their homework. They also give them a free piece of fruit for those who don't have an afternoon snack.

The Xarxa de les Biblioteques de les Coses de Vic (Library of Things Network) has a particular vision of education and services. It is a community network for lending objects of occasional use – such as tools, clothes, games or musical instruments – that promotes circular economy, community sovereignty, eco-social transition and the democratization of access to resources. Through the affordable and temporary rental of these materials from the online catalogue, a second life is given to objects outside the traditional commercial circuit, promoting an alternative and responsible form of consumption, recycling and shared use. This service not only facilitates practical learning and is committed to sustainability, but also generates community ties, encourages citizen participation and creates opportunities for vulnerable groups. In collaboration with other social entities in the territory, this library is aligned with community development plans, connecting sustainability, inclusion and collaborative culture.

The Network is made up of 6 libraries, run by five social and/or cooperative organizations (La Fera Ferotge, Ashes, Tapís, La Creu Roja and La Clota):

- Library of tools: self-repairing, carpentry, DIY...
- Furniture library: for decorative use (sideboards, occasional events).
- Clothes library: sporadic use and complements.
- Care Library: items for temporary use (strollers, crutches, wheelchairs...).
- Music library: musical complements (cables, loudspeakers...).
- Games library: table games and other types of dynamics.

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On the other hand, the Biblioteca Miramargés is the library of the University of Vic registered in the University Library Network of Catalonia (Xarxa de Biblioteques Universitàries de Catalunya, CSUC). Although its mission is not explicitly defined, it plays a key role in the field of education and support for the university community and citizens from the age of 16. It is a space for meetings, collaborative work (coworking spaces) and access to information resources. They also offer individualized attention programmes for teachers, researchers and students, as well as other cultural activities in collaboration with other educational agents (Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés, bookshops in the city, publishers).

2) Challenges

Despite the advances and inspiring initiatives that have been transforming libraries into more open educational, social and community spaces, several structural and strategic challenges remain. These challenges reflect the tensions and opportunities that emerge in the process of adapting to the new educational, cultural and social needs of citizens. The following four axes summarize the main challenges identified from the interviews and the documentary analysis:

1. Visibility and impact of the service

- Lack of dissemination of services.
- Improving communication with the educational value of the projects to make it more visible inside and outside the institutions.
- Consolidating the service as a safe meeting place, a place of communication, a place to find quality information, as an engine that generates and transforms activities.
- Connecting school visits to libraries with the school's educational project.
- Rethinking internal indicators to improve the assessment of the impact of the service.

2. Development of the training offer

- Currently, social function predominates over formal learning. The educational and self-learning dimension needs to be strengthened (Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés).
- Ignasi Janer (director) says that 'as a social centre, we are already making a lot of progress. But as an educational centre, I think we need to grow much more, even more. Therefore, there is still an imbalance.'
- Training projects (video games, digital training with the elderly, and musicals) are slightly developed by public libraries but have little presence in university libraries.

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- Reconsidering a more comprehensive advisory model for researchers in university libraries.
- Extending the number of online training courses in university faculties to reach more people.

3. Enforcing educational and cultural alliances

- Lack of collaboration with other cultural facilities and venues.
- Increasing cooperation with universities.
- Little activity with secondary schools due to a lack of teaching interest and/or little training of librarians in dealing with adolescents.
- Creating a meeting point between faculties and the Student Council to identify the needs and expectations of the university library service.

4. Facilitation of services and resources

- Reversing the decline in physical loans and increasing digital loans of verified bibliographic references in university libraries.

Thus, among the challenges facing the educational role of libraries is the need to expand their pedagogical functions by consolidating them as a space for learning and integral development, increase the visibility of their services, consolidate solid educational alliances and define quality indicators to evaluate their impact.

3) Associated Indicators

Policy dimension

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
<p>Are libraries identified as actors for lifelong learning and education?</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>The model of libraries of XBM preserves the essence of libraries and innovates in the methodologies of services oriented to lifelong learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourages the reading habits and competence of any person regardless of age and origin. - Facilitates universal access to information, culture and knowledge. A space for the generation of knowledge. - Gives support to continuous training. - Meeting place and community space. <p>The relationship between the needs and interests of citizens and access to guaranteed social equality and knowledge is represented in four areas of strategic action, in accordance with the activity carried out there: Discover, Learn, Create and Share.</p> <p>Each area of strategic action is related to a space:</p> <p>A library to discover: a space of inspiration.</p> <p>A library to learn: learning space.</p> <p>A library to create: a space for creation.</p> <p>A library to share: a meeting space.</p>

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Are libraries part of community development plans?	Yes	<p>The libraries of the Diputació act as key players in local and community development. They do so through the creation of citizen laboratories (BiblioLab), aligning themselves with the objectives of cohesion, innovation and local sustainability. BiblioLab is a programme of the Xarxa de Biblioteques Municipals (XBM) that develops and supports actions aimed at providing access to knowledge through experimentation and innovative and creative methodologies in a collaborative environment open to the public. BiblioLab is one of the five outstanding projects of 'Connectem', the action plan of the 2016–2019 mandate of the Diputació de Barcelona. With this programme, the Corporation aims to encourage creativity and creativity in citizens, skills of great value in the development of people in areas such as education, culture and entrepreneurship. It will do so under the criteria of equal access, economic sustainability, efficiency, quality of service and relevance; taking advantage of and enhancing the resources and networked work of libraries, facilities close to the citizen and linked to the territory.</p>
Are libraries included in OER/Open Science/Open Data policy?	Yes	<p>The Miramarges Library (University of Vic), in collaboration with the Consorci de Biblioteques Universitàries de Catalunya, already has a data repository that allows researchers to publish their research data in open</p>

		<p>access. Although this area is still in its infancy, they are preparing to ensure that these data are well labelled and documented, following FAIR principles.</p> <p>Although demand is currently low, they predict that it will increase, especially because many funded projects already explicitly require data to be made available in open repositories. For this reason, the library is prepared to accompany the teaching staff, although it will be necessary to assess whether, in the future, they will be able to provide this support in a generalized way.</p>
Cooperation with schools/universities at the national or international level	Yes	<p>In the province of Barcelona, there is extensive cooperation between primary schools (including nursery schools) and public libraries. It is a very active relationship with great potential. As indicated by the professionals of the Diputació de Barcelona, 'There are libraries that are committed to continuity beyond the library itself, providing academic support'. The activities can be divided into three blocks:</p> <p>School visits: a growing and continuous activity.</p> <p>Workshops and specific activities: such as escape rooms, activities on disinformation, and international projects (ex: with LEGO and sustainability).</p> <p>Educational support spaces: such as the 'Club dels deures' (Homework club) in Canovelles.</p>

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		The relationship with universities is weaker, often limited to its use as a study room for university students. However, there are some alliances which are described below.
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A relevant case is the Escola, Biblioteca i Universitat (School, Library and University) programme at the Pilarín Bayés Library in Vic, which is run jointly with the University of Vic and which, under the supervision of university lecturers and school teachers, brings together children from Vic's schools and future teachers to work on language issues in the library. It is undoubtedly an ideal place because of its architectural characteristics and because of its content, books and language.

Another example of cooperation between libraries and universities is the one between the library of Sant Adrià (Sant Adrià de Besòs) and the University of Barcelona. It is a campaign of 'Service Learning', with workshops on educational topics carried out by students of the Faculty of Pedagogy of the University of Barcelona at the library.

Finally, we found the project **Llegim el riu** (Reading the river), which brings together citizenship and ecological research on rivers through social innovation spaces created in municipal libraries to promote knowledge of river ecosystems and citizen collaboration in their protection. Llegim el riu is a transversal project of the Library Services Management and the Environmental Services Management of the Diputació de Barcelona, the city councils and the municipal libraries. The project is coordinated with the citizen science tool RiuNet from the research group (FEHMLab) of the Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences at the University of Barcelona, and is supported by the association Hàbitats and the Rivus Foundation.

Llegim el riu aims to complement the citizen science projects in the Llobregat river basin and the Besòs and Tordera river basins, in order to promote the knowledge and collaboration of citizens in their protection. With the results of this scientific and informative process, recommendations for public policies to manage and conserve the fluvial heritage of these areas are to be shared with the public.

Public and Educational Impact

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Number of students/teachers visiting a university library per year	Yes	In 2024 there were a total of 16,262 school visits to the public libraries of the Diputació de Barcelona, with a total of 337,086 students attending these visits.

Per capita averages for the population served

	2022	2023	2024
Visits per inhabitant	2,4	2,9	2,9
Use of the loan service per inhabitant	0,5	0,5	0,6
In-person loans per inhabitant	1,7	1,9	2,0
Online loans per inhabitant	0,1	0,2	0,2
Computer stations per 10,000 inhabitants	11,9	12,1	12,0
Surface area per 10,000 inhabitants	506	505	502
Documents per inhabitant	1,7	1,7	1,7

Percentages over population and visits

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% of registered population 39% 38% 35%

Uses of the loan service in relation to visits 20% 19% 19%

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries working with NGOs, educational institutions, associations?	Yes	<p>In addition to the collaborations with schools and universities mentioned in the previous section, some libraries also cooperate with NGOs and other associations. For example, the Xarxa de Biblioteca de les Coses (Library of Things) regularly collaborates with 5 such organizations: Fera Ferotge, la Creu Roja, Ashes Association, Tapís Association and La Clota.</p> <p>In this area, Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés stands out, with several projects carried out jointly with different institutions. With the Sant Tomàs Association, the Clubs de lectura en veu alta (Oral Book Clubs) have been created. This year, three collaborations have been carried out at the digital creation laboratories with educational centres in Vic: Two collaborations have been carried out with the Escola d'Art de Vic (Arts School), within the framework of the educational innovation programme CooperArt of the Department of Education of the Generalitat de Catalunya. These have been with the Higher Grade in Interactive Graphics</p>

		and Animation for Video Games. The third collaboration was with the UVic-UCC's Degree in Multimedia and Video Game Design. Another initiative of the library in collaboration with various areas of the City Council of Vic and the involvement of social, sports, cultural and health organizations and associations of the city and the region is La Biblioteca Humana (The Human Library).
User satisfaction related to the Library	Yes	According to the latest survey carried out by the Diputació de Barcelona, the level of user satisfaction with municipal libraries in the province of Barcelona is high (Diputació de Barcelona, 2020). From this report, it is also worth noting that 76% of users make use of the lending service, and almost half-read books or consult documents in the library. The main reasons for visiting them are leisure (40%), study (34%) and self-education (31%). These motivations are also linked to a high level of satisfaction.
Collections of electronic vs. physical books		The total number of physical documentary sources in XBMB in 2024 was 9,758,664.

b) Participation and Democratic Culture, including Social Inclusion and Equal Access

1) Overview

Nicolás Barbieri, professor at the UOC and recognized researcher on cultural rights, states that, in Catalonia, *'Libraries are the second most powerful democratic*

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institution, after the fire brigade. He considers that the role of libraries has transcended access to books and access to timely information, becoming today, in some cases, spaces for critical support, the production of knowledge and the promotion of cultural rights. Libraries play an active role in reducing cultural inequalities, because, as Barbieri explains, *'They try to break down some of the hierarchies and inequalities that are very typical of the cultural sector.'* As we have said, at this time of transition, attempts to go beyond traditional library practices, frameworks and concepts are highly significant. However, as Barbieri points out, they require a rethinking of the old in order to experiment with the new, a process of social and educational innovation that is not always easy to implement nor universally accepted by all stakeholders.

In general terms, these transformations are driven by committed professionals and by a vision of the library as a key institution for social justice and citizen empowerment. Libraries are claimed as living and welcoming cultural centres, where not only content is disseminated (access), but also generated (use and production). Libraries can be spaces of cultural production, where one can read, but also write, express oneself and create. Therefore, they can become a space for community participation, where people can share their knowledge and experiences.

A vision that is also shared by the Diputació de Barcelona, which considers libraries to be social, meetings and democratic spaces, in the sense that they guarantee access to information, reading and knowledge for everyone. Another characteristic highlighted by the Provincial Council is that of neutrality. Libraries are neutral institutions, with their own values, but where anyone can find their own interests, regardless of their political persuasion. This neutrality also provides security to its users.

In short, today the public library is not only a cultural facility: it is a living instrument of social transformation and a key institution for the construction of a democratic, fair and inclusive culture. The idea that public libraries must play an active role in identifying and overcoming inequalities has been consolidating, as these often invisible inequalities hinder real access to information and cultural life, especially for vulnerable groups. For this reason, the library has begun to position itself, progressively but decisively, as an agent that accompanies access to information with minimum quality criteria and, at the same time, as a space that contributes to guaranteeing fundamental cultural rights.

It is worth noting that, among all cultural institutions, the library is probably the one with the greatest potential to become a real space for the exercise of democracy, in which everyone has access and the opportunity to participate. As Nicolás Barbieri states throughout the interview, the library 'promotes a culture based on recognition,

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coexistence, speech and participation'. In other words, it generates a community out of diversity, while building safe spaces for debate.

The Biblioteca de les Coses (Library of Things), for example, acts as an inclusive and participatory space that promotes democratic culture through the collaborative allocation of resources and shared management. This model fosters equal opportunities, free access to common goods and shared citizenship. In this library, the participation of the community is articulated through various mechanisms: the donation of objects, volunteering and direct involvement in the creation and facilitation of services. In addition, there is a desire to create thematic micro-communities around each library, such as tools, clothes or furniture, in order to strengthen social ties and a sense of belonging. Social entities play a key role here, with a clear desire to generate networks of collaboration and mutual support between organizations in the area. Furthermore, these spaces are consolidated as meeting, training and relationship-building points, thus reinforcing social inclusion and community cohesion.

On a social level, the Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés is undertaking a recognized task that is necessary and essential given the context of the city and neighbourhood where the library is located. As its director says: *'What is happening in Vic is happening here (in the library). I don't know how many square metres Vic has, but here, in 4,000 square metres, you see a parcel of Vic. No, not a part... No, everything. If there are problems, we can see them here too. The library is a clear reflection of the city where we are.'*

The Pilarín Bayés and Montseny libraries stand out for their commitment to the inclusion of ethnic, cultural and generational diversity. They are both welcoming spaces that promote respect for diversity and adapt both the activities and the spaces to this socio-political outlook. To make this approach effective, they have intentionally incorporated professionals specialized in the care of people, such as social educators, who play a key role in welcoming, especially children and adolescents, in promoting coexistence among users and in generating educational, social and cultural opportunities for people in vulnerable situations.

The existence of the 12 mobile libraries throughout the province of Barcelona is also a commitment to inclusion, in the sense of offering territorial equality to guarantee access to information, reading and knowledge for everyone. The 'bibliobusos' are mobile libraries on buses that travel periodically along a pre-established route of towns in a specific geographical area. This type of mobile library is designed for municipalities with between 300 and 2,700 inhabitants, with fewer cultural and educational opportunities. These are municipalities that do not have a stable library and can offer their users services in the same conditions as public libraries in larger areas with stable library services.

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At the international level, contrasting interviews have shown how libraries are a space for everyone, open-door spaces for the citizens around them, not aimed at a specific sector of the population. They are a common good in general, a public service dictated by law. The libraries of Medellín, like those of the Fundació Ratón Biblioteca, are places of security, of trust, of meetings and of community. This idea of security is repeated in all interviews with international experts. In the case of Medellín, they are spaces where violence does not enter and, therefore, children and adolescents feel safe.

In the case of Lisbon, security has other connotations associated with the importance of physical space. In the words of Tatiana Sanches, from the library of the University of Lisbon: *'Libraries are a secure place to be. So, we will always have students here physically, because, first, they are secure, and this is very important to anyone, and mostly to foreign students who are displaced and out of their homes and families...they are alone in their academic path.'* Tatiana Sanches also comments that the library is inclusive because it does not make distinctions or discriminations, and few institutions can claim this: *'We don't ask anyone what they will read, why and when or what they will do.'* Therefore, the library provides and protects both physical and intellectual freedoms.

Finally, it is necessary to highlight Barbieri's warnings in the face of attacks and censorship by regressive groups and the impact of budget cuts. In this context, libraries will have to take an active stance to defend and preserve their role as essential spaces for the exercise of democracy.

2) Challenges

The commitment of libraries to social transformation, inclusion and universal access to culture has positioned these spaces as key players in the promotion of social justice and cultural rights. However, this process of redefining their role entails a series of structural and practical challenges. From the interviews conducted and the reports collected, various challenges are identified that hinder the full development of this new library model. These challenges can be grouped into four main thematic areas:

1. Inclusion and cultural diversity

- Limited access to the cultural diversity of children and young people, especially those from diverse origins, due to a lack of active strategies to link them and saturation of the service.

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- Difficulty in establishing a real and effective intercultural dialogue: lack of proposals centred on oral and other forms of cultural expression that facilitate access to diverse groups.
- Social integration of libraries with the local community through culture (music, orality, reading...), is still to be consolidated.
- Access to communities in impoverished and complex social contexts begins with community work that helps to create trust in that space (for example, the Montseny library in Vic). The challenge is how to achieve social integration with the community through diversified forms of culture that help to link them to each other. In the Marvila library in Lisbon, in a neighbourhood surrounded by 11 social neighbourhoods, with 80% of people of Roma ethnicity and with strong economic problems, the library achieves this through resources that provide job opportunities. Pedro Torres, librarian at this library, states that the most important thing is to ensure that in this space young people find opportunities that connect them with curiosity, a desire to learn and that they feel they have a sense of recognition from their own community. He concludes: 'We want to come to the library to be an opportunity to grow personally and to achieve social improvement.'

2. Community participation and governance

- Absence of a real self-management model that actively involves volunteers and other community agents.
- Insufficient participatory governance, especially with regard to the involvement of children and young people in decision making and in generational relations.
- Lack of links between the different internal library services.

3. Resources and operational capacity

- Lack of human and technical resources to fully develop the social role of libraries.
- Absence of key technical figures (such as facilitators or communicators) that allow flexible scheduling, design adapted strategies and respond to the changing needs of the territory.

4. Political positioning and strategic alliances

- To build alliances with other social, educational or institutional networks (town councils, universities, local entities...).
- The need to confront eventual attacks or ideological pressures, especially in regressive contexts, and to defend the role of libraries as spaces for the free exercise of democracy.

The future of libraries as active agents of social transformation depends on addressing these challenges strategically. Three areas emerge as priorities: guaranteeing real inclusion in cultural diversity, strengthening models of participatory governance with the community, and providing libraries with the human and technical resources necessary to deploy their transformative potential. All of this, without forgetting the need for a firm stance to preserve their role as safe, free and democratic spaces.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries identified by the State as a key actor to promote democratic culture?	Yes	At the Montseny library, during the activities for children, an assembly space is held in which participation is encouraged, although this process is still in the process of consolidation. The children are invited to express their opinions and, for example, at the end of the afternoon, they are offered free play time so that they can make decisions about the activities. Even so, it is recognized that it is difficult to achieve equal participation, as there are always some children who take part more than others or not all proposals are accepted. They are working to diversify the activities and prevent the dynamics from being based solely on games such as football. As far as families are concerned, quarterly meetings are held, as well as maintaining daily contact during the activities.

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Are libraries integrating SDG Framework?	Yes	Biblioteca de les Coses (Library of Things) contributes to SDGs, such as environmental sustainability (SDG 12: Responsible production and consumption) through the promotion of the circular economy and the reuse of objects, as well as SDG 10 (reducing inequalities) by promoting equal access.
Are there policies in favour of social inclusion and accessibility?	Yes	Projects for families and children in vulnerable situations. These are projects to break down the 'postcode' barrier and reduce inequalities of origin. The Biblioteca de les Coses collaborates with entities that work with young people in the process of labour insertion and in psychosocial risk conditions. Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés has programmes for functional adaptations (sign language, Braille for the blind, physical accessibility, etc.).
Do libraries promote lifelong learning?	Yes	Libraries offer informal, accessible and personalized learning that involves little bureaucracy. The library assumes a role in 'lifelong learning' and in the promotion of autonomous learning. The clearest and most common example in several libraries is that of the large number of elderly people who attend daily to learn about computing topics (digital literacy).

<p>Are users involved in service design?</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>In the process of creating new libraries, the vision of the community is often integrated into close collaboration with the city council. Public libraries are expected to understand and respond to citizens' needs at every stage—from the conception and design of facilities to the management, delivery, and evaluation of services. Citizen participation should guide both the improvement of existing services and the creation and implementation of new library spaces and offerings. The participatory methodologies used will vary depending on the type of information sought and the stakeholders involved at each stage of engagement. There are several notable examples of this approach:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The future central library of Sant Cugat del Vallès**, to be located in Ramon Barnils Park, was developed through a participatory process. Local residents were actively involved in deciding the spaces and functions that the library will include.- In other cases, such as in Castelldefels or Cornellà, existing libraries have been rethought through participatory processes.- A particularly innovative example is the redesign of youth spaces in the Biblioteca de Nou Barris through the 9B Espai Jove project. This initiative aimed to create a participatory model for designing and transforming youth spaces in libraries, beginning with the Nou Barris and Zona Nord branches. It started with a prototype
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		<p>intended for these two locations but was conceived as a replicable model for any library wishing to reimagine its spaces for young users. Importantly, the project redefines youth spaces not as isolated or segregated zones, but as integral extensions of the library – designed to serve young people while remaining connected to the broader library environment.</p>
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c) Spatial Design and Shared Spaces

1) Overview

The spatial design of libraries varies according to their mission and social context, but the need to rethink spaces in order to respond to current challenges is increasingly evident. Beyond their traditional function, libraries are seeking to develop safe, open and flexible spaces, capable of hosting a variety of activities and encouraging social cohesion.

Miramarges Library at the University of Vic, coworking areas and collaborative workspaces are available, but a lack of learning spaces has been identified, along with the need to reorganize existing areas to allow for more flexible use and to overcome architectural barriers. A centralized management of faculty spaces is also being considered in order to improve accessibility.

Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés of Vic is committed to an open and interconnected design, with a distribution of spaces for groups and activities (studying, meeting up, and quietness), minimizing signage and encouraging shared responsibility. Social interaction and coexistence are articulated through educators and protocols of conduct.

Xarxa de les Biblioteques de les Coses of Vic presents a decentralized and strategically located model in different entities of the city. These multi-purpose spaces and workshops reinforce the link with local associations and encourage community interaction. However, there is a lack of a central coordinating space that articulates the

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network and a willingness to offer training activities, such as workshops in restoration or sewing, in collaboration with other neighbourhood facilities.

The case of **Santo Domingo (Colombia)** illustrates a contrasting reality: libraries without permanent infrastructure, operating through an itinerant pedagogist. This model, which emerged in Latin America as a direct response to social exclusion, aims to deliver library services and cultural activities to areas lacking fixed facilities, particularly in vulnerable neighbourhoods. Using mobile units and community-based initiatives, it promotes access to reading, culture and knowledge from an inclusive, flexible and context-adapted perspective. From the point of view of the public library system of Medellín, while infrastructure remains important, it presents significant challenges in terms of sustainability – underscoring the relevance and value of this alternative model.

Libraries can reproduce internal segregation (spaces divided by incompatible uses or rigid separations) and are subject to institutional tensions over the control of public space. It is therefore essential to rethink them as shared learning spaces, with collaborative management that depends less on individual leadership and more on a community-based approach.

2) Challenges

The design of library spaces is not only an architectural question, but also a pedagogical, social and political one. The physical configuration directly influences the way people interact, learn and live. In the current context, libraries aspire to develop flexible, welcoming and open spaces, able to respond to a variety of needs and to accommodate collaborative practices. However, the cases analysed show that this transformation is not automatic and that various obstacles must be overcome in order to make a shared and inclusive model of space a reality. These obstacles can be grouped into three main thematic areas:

1. Inclusive and functional design of spaces

- Persistence of architectural barriers that hinder accessibility and flexibility of use.
- Physical space limitations in small libraries.
- Under-utilisation of spaces due to lack of adaptation or bureaucratic conditions.
- Pressure for multiple uses that are not always compatible and internal segregation between areas for silence, study, meeting or community activities.
- Lack of specific spaces for training and collaborative work.

2. Collaborative and decentralized management

- Excessive dependence on individual management to implement a shared space model.
- Absence of a central coordination space to better articulate the Libraries of Things network (Xarxa de les Biblioteques de les Coses).
- Lack of systematization of protocols for action in the face of conflicts and of mechanisms to guarantee a safe environment.
- Institutional tendency to control public space.

3. Territorial articulation and networked work

- Lack of coordination with other facilities in the neighbourhood that could enrich the use of the space.

The most urgent challenges identified in relation to the spatial design of libraries are, firstly, the need to rethink the spaces with the logic of accessibility and real multifunctionality; secondly, the consolidation of collaborative management models that do not depend exclusively on individual leadership; and, finally, the construction of territorial networks that allow resources, activities and communities to be shared. Progress in these areas is key to making libraries true spaces for learning, coexistence and democracy.

3) Associated indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries building inclusive spaces?	Yes	The aim of Biblioteques Inclusive (Inclusive Libraries) project is to raise awareness of aspects of accessibility to Catalan public libraries so that they become inclusive spaces that offer opportunities for the future to all people with disabilities in order to ensure their full integration into society. Public libraries have an important role as agents of inclusion and must guarantee the universal right of access to information, culture and reading. The project works along four different lines of action: — Architecture: accessible physical and technological equipment at service desks,

		<p>such as magnetic loops for people with hearing impairments, adapted height desks, Braille signage, and appropriate furniture, used both by the public and by organizations serving people with disabilities. Efforts have also been made to implement signposting that makes libraries more accessible to all people, including those with visual, cognitive, intellectual or learning disabilities. An example of this includes identification signs with universal pictograms for doors, opening hours, directories and sections (novels, comics, baby library...), facilitating spatial understanding for diverse audiences.</p> <p>— Documentary collections and support materials: libraries offer computer accessibility aids for people with disabilities or mobility difficulties, such as keyboards with large or small keys, adapted mice, joysticks, key guards to avoid accidental key presses, and specialized software such as JAWS and Braille lines.</p> <p>— Activities and services. Best practices in inclusive services aim to guarantee adapted and equitable attention to users with disabilities or specific needs, offering diversified materials and adapted formats (home lending and reading, accessible formats in Braille, pictograms, easy-to-read materials, audio books, DVDs with subtitles and sign language interpretation); accessible information on activities and services through various channels and formats: face-to-face, online, with multimodal communication and tutorials adapted to the catalogue; cooperation with specialized groups and local entities to</p>
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		identify needs, design collaborative services and raise awareness through workshops or exhibitions on functional diversity.
Are libraries creating places for minorities?	Yes	Biblioteca del Fondo in Santa Coloma de Gramanet was built in a neighbourhood with a great ethnic diversity. It was designed as a library over a market, with a large kitchen as a space for community activities. It is a political strategy to attract, especially the immigrant women's community to the municipal library.
Are libraries accessible to people with disabilities? Yes.	Yes	The county council's libraries offer Braille maps in buildings that allow users to find their way around without visual aids. There is also tactile and large print signage, as new features in the libraries of Rubí and Terrassa, which help people with ASD and visual impairment to identify the spaces, including the relocation of collections (large print, adapted with pictograms).
How many hours are the libraries open?		<p>Opening days per week: between 5 and 7 days, depending on the library.</p> <p>Daily opening hours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Morning (weekdays): about 4 hours (9:30 AM – 1:30 PM). — Afternoon (weekdays): about 4.5 hours (3:30 PM – 8:00/8:30 PM). — Saturdays: 4 hours in the morning (+ 4 hours in the afternoon in some libraries). — Sundays: 4 hours in the morning (+ afternoon in selected study rooms). — Evening/Monday to Thursday: until 11:30 PM, study rooms only. <p>Depending on the library, this means between 30 and 40 hours a week of regular public access, with extended hours</p>

		if we include study hours and Saturdays/holidays.
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d) Digital Technologies and Information Access

1) Overview

Libraries are spaces that seek to guarantee equal access to digital tools and resources. Moreover, in many regions, they have played and continue to play a key role in digital training and in providing critical support to citizens in the use of information.

The rapid technological evolution, the emergence of the Internet and the consolidation of electronic books have forced libraries to constantly reinvent themselves. As Marta Cano, manager of the XBMB (Barcelona Library Network), says, *'I believe that libraries have evolved because we are always in crisis.'*

This process has entailed a transition from physical to digital format, as well as a change in uses and media: from lending books, CDs or DVDs to accessing platforms such as YouTube, Netflix or other digital resources. Moreover, the nature of knowledge has also changed, as it is no longer only transmitted, but generated by users themselves.

Along these lines, various projects promoted by the XBMB stand out, with objectives such as prescribing educational video games that do not incite violence, recommending music outside the commercial market, encouraging critical reflection on the Internet and combating disinformation.

Given this reality, one of the main challenges is the high level of digital illiteracy among parts of the population. At Biblioteca Pilarín Bayés, this challenge is met through the l'Oficina d'Atenció Ciutadana (Citizen Service Office), although it is acknowledged that the service is insufficient to meet all the demands.

The digital divide has both an intergenerational and a cultural dimension. For example, at Xarxa de les Biblioteques de les Coses (Library of Things), it has been detected that online services do not reach all the public, which has highlighted the need to reinforce face-to-face and physical communication.

The most recent challenge is the emergence of artificial intelligence tools, which require more in-depth development of critical and reflective digital literacy.

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Current services:

- Digital literacy.
- Laptop lending.
- Digital training.
- Technological projects: disinformation, video games, critical reflection on the Internet.
- Courses on the use of information.
- Bibliographic managers.
- ICT activities: video editing.

2) Challenges

Libraries play a fundamental role in equitable access to information and digital technologies. In a context of rapid change – with the expansion of the Internet, the emergence of new formats and the arrival of artificial intelligence – they are constantly challenged to renew themselves. These technological transformations affect not only the media, but also learning practices, forms of cultural consumption and relations with the public. In the face of this reality, various challenges related to digital literacy, accessibility and the construction of critical thinking in the use of information are emerging:

1. Digital literacy and competences

- Increase citizens' digital skills to avoid new forms of exclusion.
- Develop specific training on the critical use of artificial intelligence.

2. Accessibility and digital inclusion

- Equal and free access to digital resources.
- Strengthen the dissemination of digital services through physical and in-person channels to reach more citizens.
- Improve online services, such as the digital catalogue, to make them more intuitive and participative.

3. Critical thinking and information sovereignty

- Develop projects that encourage reflection on digital consumption, disinformation and responsible use of the Internet.
- Generate community-based mechanisms that help to identify relevant and reliable information in an environment of information overload.

- To give prominence to alternative cultural content and practices (music, video games, etc.) that encourage a critical and diverse perspective.

The main current challenges focus, firstly, on overcoming digital illiteracy to ensure real technological inclusion; secondly, on developing critical literacy in the face of phenomena such as artificial intelligence and disinformation; and, finally, ensuring accessibility to digital services, both in terms of tools and communication. These challenges are not only technical, but also profoundly social and democratic.

3) Associated indicators incorporate more information

Policy

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Do libraries have a role in digital skills and digital literacy?	Yes	They are spaces to help solve vital needs such as the use of social networks and computers. Spaces to learn to search for information but also to create it.
How many workshops/training sessions are there for digital literacy?		<p>Many workshops are held on a regular basis as part of the 'Connecta't' programme offered by the council's libraries. These focus on digital literacy, culture and e-administration procedures. Within the Connecta't programme, the following workshops are offered:</p> <p>To learn about devices and the Internet:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Managing apps and device memory - Basic functions and settings of mobile devices - Making the most of email and advancing its use <p>For leisure purposes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Editing videos on a mobile phone - Apps for physical and emotional well-being - Editing photos on a mobile phone - Online shopping <p>For communication:</p>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Using your mobile phone to make video calls- Creating presentations with online digital tools- Professional social media networks Workshops held to date: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Learning to code with family- Fake news: don't be misled- Protecting your digital identity and security: phishing, pharming and spam- Programming Virtual Reality- Introduction to coding: basic programming structures.
Collection 2024		Computer workstations: 7,094 Daily usage of public Internet and office software access services: 2,544 Daily usage of Wi-Fi service: 5,512 Loans (in-person and virtual services combined): 48,573

3. SWOT Analysis

Dimension	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Role of libraries in learning and education	<p>A space for informal intergenerational education that plays a central role in the educational ecosystem.</p> <p>A living machine of social transformation with the function of encouraging reading, producing knowledge, critical information literacy and promoting cultural rights.</p> <p>Mature and resilient library system with library leadership.</p> <p>(Natalia Duque, Medellín).</p>	<p>Mission is not well defined.</p> <p>Lack of qualitative indicators to evaluate its function.</p> <p>Lack of institutional recognition of its educational role.</p> <p>Lack of inter-institutional educational networks.</p> <p>Precarious working conditions that can affect the quality of the service (Natalia Duque, Medellín).</p>	<p>To extend its pedagogical functions.</p> <p>Potential to foster collaborative and educational projects in partnership with the educational community.</p> <p>Promotion of community learning policies.</p> <p>Promote diverse cultural dissemination platforms.</p> <p>Extend the number of online training courses in university faculties to reach more people.</p>	<p>Political changes that deprioritize its educational function.</p> <p>Budget cuts or lack of specific funding for educational programmes.</p> <p>Dependence on volunteers and local social entities.</p> <p>Decline in physical loans.</p>

<p>Participation and democratic culture, including Social Inclusion and Equal Access</p>	<p>Meeting space open to citizen participation.</p> <p>A cultural centre for community life and a safe haven aiming to reduce cultural and educational inequalities.</p> <p>Libraries are the second most powerful democratic institution (Nicolás Barbieri).</p> <p>Universal, free and territorial access.</p> <p>People-centred intergenerational meeting points.</p> <p>Accessible activities and spaces</p> <p>Attention to diversity.</p> <p>Links with social integration organizations.</p> <p>System that responds to community demands (ex: opening on weekdays due to social demand) (Natalia Duque, Medellín).</p>	<p>Little citizen involvement due to the loss of the collective sense of the library as a common good.</p> <p>Low visibility and difficulties in reaching less involved groups.</p> <p>Lack of diversity of professionals.</p> <p>Absence of anticipated inclusion policies.</p> <p>Difficulty in reaching more vulnerable groups if active links are not established.</p> <p>Limited resources to ensure full accessibility.</p> <p>Architectural barriers.</p> <p>Social pressures that conflict with labour and administrative constraints (Natalia Duque, Medellín).</p>	<p>Reinforce the role of libraries as safe spaces for debate, community expression and coexistence.</p> <p>Potential to become a civic reference point and a driver of social cohesion.</p> <p>Promote shared governance processes with users, overcoming the passive user model.</p> <p>Developing inclusive policies.</p> <p>Networking with social services and community organizations.</p> <p>Culturally and linguistically adapted activities: promoting oral proposals to reach different cultures.</p> <p>Broaden audiences and adapt services to diversities.</p> <p>Partnerships with public institutions.</p>	<p>Attacks and censorship by reactionary groups.</p> <p>Political disengagement.</p> <p>Growing individualism and lack of time/citizen involvement.</p> <p>Perception of the library as a welfare or social assistance service.</p> <p>Stigmatization of the library as a resource for vulnerable populations.</p> <p>Resource constraints for sustainable inclusive actions.</p> <p>Cultural barriers and social prejudices that hinder access or full participation.</p>
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<p>Spatial design and shared spaces</p>	<p>Open and collaborative work spaces.</p> <p>Areas for different uses and groups.</p> <p>Multi-purpose community meeting spaces.</p>	<p>Physical space limitations in small libraries.</p> <p>Architectural conditions that hinder flexibility.</p> <p>Spaces are underused or conditioned by bureaucracy.</p> <p>Internal segregation of the library: separate spaces for reading, spaces for shared activities.</p>	<p>Extend the number of spaces.</p> <p>Collaboration with other facilities in the neighbourhood.</p> <p>Versatile redesigns.</p> <p>Improving the management of shared learning spaces.</p>	<p>Institutional tendency to control public space.</p> <p>Pressure from incompatible multiple uses.</p> <p>Underutilization if not properly managed.</p>
<p>Digital technologies and access to information</p>	<p>Equal and free access to digital resources.</p> <p>Training in digital literacy.</p> <p>Critical information literacy.</p>	<p>Digital training is still insufficient.</p> <p>Limited development of critical tools for using AI.</p> <p>High level of digital illiteracy among users.</p> <p>Obsolete technological resources.</p>	<p>Expand training in digital skills.</p> <p>Improving access to digital resources.</p> <p>Develop technological projects and training on AI.</p> <p>Generate community mechanisms to identify relevant and reliable information in the face of information overabundance.</p> <p>Partnerships with local technological entities.</p>	<p>Technological dependence without training support.</p> <p>Persistent digital divide.</p>

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4. Conclusion

In this first exploratory study of public libraries in the province of Barcelona (Spain), we have found that they are in transition. Since the 1990s and 2000s, Spanish libraries have been moving away from being (only) a repository of books or other information materials and towards becoming something different. And this transition is not over. At the present time, we can see the enormous vitality of libraries with multiple initiatives that direct them towards spaces for shared learning, community, participation, (self-) learning, well-being, promotion of critical thinking, democracy, etc. (Pechtelidis and Kioupiolis, 2020.) This is a highly positive element that demonstrates the enormous potential of libraries to achieve what the IFLA Manifesto proposes (2022). Precisely because public libraries are in this transition space without a defined and fixed model, the Libcommon project is more relevant than ever with the proposal that this shared vision continues to move towards libraries as common goods, intimately linked to an idea of all education, formal, non-formal and informal, as common goods (UNESCO, 2015).

On the one hand, Klininberg (2020) stresses the enormous potential of libraries as commons, as the people's palaces. However, as we have seen in the SWOT analysis, the challenges are still very significant. As Richard Sennett explained in *Together* (2012), for example, the complexity of living, coexisting, sharing and interacting together with different and unequal people is considerable. And this will not happen by spontaneous generation. It is necessary that the library agenda as a common good (Ostrom, 1990; Steiner and Holley, 2009) becomes a shared horizon for all professionals, participants, and communities. Libraries can become a true common good, provided that both the enabling conditions and their orientation are actively developed. This, according to the classic analysis of Bollier (2014) implies, at the same time: a) being a shared, open good increasingly self-governed by the community itself (common); b) generating shared dynamics and relationships among diverse and unequal people – that is, contributing to the creation of diverse community bonds (commons), of social capital, *bridging* (Putnam, 2001); and c) promoting subjectivities, attitudes, values, visions, and norms that differ from neoliberal ones, which view libraries as an individual, competitive, and instrumental resource (commoning) (Ostrom and Hess, 2008). In this sense, and as the expert Barbieri stated in the interviews, it is perhaps worth thinking that we should not only be attentive to advancing libraries in this sense. In this regard, and as Barbieri observes in the interviews, we must not only focus on advancing libraries in this direction but also – given the global rise of neo-fascism – consider how to maintain, protect and safeguard everything that libraries already are and do.

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Finally, it should be emphasized that university libraries, given their long-standing association with knowledge, are only just beginning this transition towards becoming a common good within the academic community. They have already launched highly significant initiatives aimed at promoting critical thinking, community engagement, well-being, and (self-) learning, yet this vision remains insufficiently defined. For this reason, we believe the LibCommon project holds particular relevance.

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Case: France

This research was based on an extensive review and analysis of existing bibliographic sources and reports concerning the current state of libraries in France. In addition, a qualitative approach was followed through semi-structured interviews with five professionals in leadership positions in French libraries, which were conducted in April 2025 remotely (via video calls) and analysed thematically. Each interview lasted approximately one hour. The objective was to record and analyse their perspectives and assessments regarding the condition and prospects of libraries in France, based on the four key axes defined by the LibCommon project.

- Julien Roche – Director of the ULille Research Library. He is also head of LIBER, the Association of European Research Libraries
- Laure Delrue – Co-director of the ULille Research Library.
- Julien Marechal – Director of the Petite Bibliothèque Ronde (Clamart, France).
- Hlne Brochard - Director of the Villeneuve d’Ascq Library.
- Silvre Mercier - Former librarian, co-founder of the association Savoircom1
- Malick Diallo – Director of the Rennes Mtropole Area Library. Vice-director of the French National Librarian Association.

1. General context

According to the French Ministry of Culture, libraries ‘*build up, preserve and promote collections of documents and objects, both physical and digital, while offering a wide range of services and activities for everyone, including people with disabilities*’.

Libraries play a crucial role in the fight against illiteracy and e-illiteracy, providing tools and training to improve reading skills and the use of digital technologies. They encourage the active participation of all publics and promote diversity by creating inclusive, open and accessible spaces, whatever the profile of users.

Libraries also contribute to the dissemination of linguistic heritage, and collaborate with various cultural, educational, social and penal institutions. They also assume responsibility for passing on to future generations the rich heritage they preserve.

Free access to cultural, educational and information resources is guaranteed to all, regardless of financial means, place of residence or level of education.

Their main missions are heritage preservation and promotion, cultural development, study and research. More specifically, they:

Preserve and make available documents (books, media, archives, etc.)

Guarantee access to culture, information and knowledge for all

Offer on-site lending and consultation

Organize cultural activities and reading education

French libraries differ mainly in the way they are supervised, their missions and the audiences they serve:

- The Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF) is the leading public institution under the authority of the French Ministry of Culture. Its mission is to build up, preserve and communicate collections, notably through legal deposit, and it plays a central role in the production of national catalogues and international cooperation. By the Ordinance of Montpellier on 28 December 1537, Francis I established a legal deposit. This act aimed to relay royal decisions, ensure the preservation of works in the service of collective memory, and, ultimately, to control the dissemination of dissident ideas (Barbier, 2013).
- Local libraries/public libraries: Managed by local authorities or groups of local authorities, they are open to all for consultation and home loans. Their administration is the responsibility of the mayor and municipal council, who set the budget, staff and regulations.
- Departmental libraries: Dependent on departmental councils, they mainly support small municipal or community libraries, particularly in rural areas.
- Academic Libraries: Under the supervision of the Ministry of Higher Education, they serve students and researchers, and participate in national documentary policy, notably through the CollEx-Persée scheme for collections of excellence. To reinforce open access, research libraries are also contributing to the Couperin Consortium,²⁹ which is dedicated to: ‘to develop access to scientific and technical information for the scientific community, by facilitating national negotiations on digital documentary resources and supporting open science’.
- School libraries: the system of ‘information and Document Centers’ (CDI). In France, the school system has its own network of libraries called ‘documentation and information centres’ (CDI). These CDIs are run by

²⁹ <https://www.couperin.org/>

documentalist teachers. The documentalist teacher’s mission is both educational and pedagogical. Through their expertise in the field of information and communication sciences (SIC), they contribute to the teaching and development of information literacy for all students.

- Other libraries: There are also community libraries and libraries in places like hospitals, prisons, corporate documentation centres or in every secondary school (also known as CDI).

The library has a strong tradition in France, as we could link the current national library as an heir to the royal library of Charles V (1368). In addition, in 1537, François 1st instituted the legal deposit system, requiring printers and booksellers to deposit printed works sold in France. The French Republic (1870–1946) and later the Fifth Republic (1958) emphasized the role of libraries in democratizing knowledge. The Bibliothèque nationale de France (BNF) became a national institution for preserving cultural heritage and promoting access to information, reinforcing the idea that education is a public good. It’s the most widespread cultural infrastructure in France, as illustrated by Figure 4:

Figure 4: Map of the libraries in France (source: Ministry of Culture)

Figure 5 is more focused on the metropolitan area:

Figure 5: Proportion of the population served by a library in 2021 by metropolitan region (source: Observatoire de la lecture publique)

Figure 5 illustrates the local dimension of libraries in France. Through this data visualization, we could have a deeper understanding of how libraries are covering the population in France. We could highlight that in Corse, in the Hauts-de-France and in the East of France, that the population has less easy access to libraries.

In parallel, 1006 university libraries cover the country. They provide access to nearly 51 million printed documents, as well as to heritage collections and electronic resources, either on-site or remotely. According to the French Ministry of High Education and Research,³⁰ University libraries are offering more than 170,000 seats; they have more than 7000 employees and they count more than 66 million entries in 2023.

Evolution of Libraries' Missions

Since 1960, the Ministry of Culture has been following the evolution and impact of libraries in France. Data from this study are published as open data³¹ and are used for the annual report.³² Public Libraries are currently ruled by the Law no.2021-1717 of December 21, 2021, on libraries and the development of public reading, commonly

³⁰ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/les-bibliotheques-de-l-enseignement-superieur-et-de-la-recherche-92796>

³¹ <https://data.culture.gouv.fr/explore/dataset/adresses-des-bibliotheques-publiques/table/>

³² <https://www.culture.gouv.fr/fr/thematiques/livre-et-lecture/pour-les-professionnels-des-bibliotheques/donnees-sur-les-bibliotheques/activites-des-bibliotheques-syntheses-annuelles>

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known as the ‘Robert Law’. This law defines libraries as essential public services provided by local authorities. Its main mission is ‘to guarantee equal access to all culture, information, education, research and leisure’.

In recent years, France has faced challenges, including funding constraints or digital divide, but libraries have been adapted by expanding digital access, promoting literacy, and fostering inclusive communities. They also play a vital role in combating misinformation, supporting democratic participation, and bridging social divides, aligning with France’s broader goals of social cohesion and cultural vitality. The system remains a symbol of public service, ensuring that education and knowledge remain accessible to all, regardless of socioeconomic background.

Nowadays the approach to learning and education is evolving significantly in both academic and public libraries. Moreover, libraries see their mission not only in terms of culture and learning, but also in terms of their ‘social performance’ (Roche, 2014).³³

His aims are to make the library a social infrastructure where people can meet and exchange ideas, as well as a resource and service offering that accompanies changes in society as a whole (changes in scientific practices in academic libraries, but also responses to the challenges of sustainable development, poverty, illiteracy, hunger, etc. in public libraries). Public libraries, for their part, are increasingly seeking to link learning, resources and the needs of their communities. Public libraries are aiming at responding to the needs of the population not only by offering resources but also by combining, for example, a social centre proposing activities for local residents, a creative and performance space, and a library with collections designed for young and old alike, and access to all media.

For instance, the Agora, a new and innovative facility in Metz (a city in eastern France), brings together a media library (municipal network of library-media libraries), a social centre (run by the Association culturelle et sociale Agora – ACS Agora) and a digital space.

The Agora (Metz) includes:

- a 120-seat creative and performance space
- a coffee and press point
- several different areas (dedicated to reading, digital technology, early childhood and social action, etc.)

³³ Roche, J. (2014). “Performance sociale et bibliothèques”. Dans J. Schöpfel et C. Boukacem-Zeghmouri *Vers la bibliothèque globale : L’Agenda 21 dans les bibliothèques* (p. 31-47). Éditions du Cercle de la Librairie. <https://doi.org/10.3917/elec.zeghm.2014.01.0031>.

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- varied collections for toddlers to adults
- access to all media, audio-visual and digital.

In academic libraries and public libraries alike, the task of imparting informational literacy to their public is becoming increasingly complex: training in artificial intelligence is adding further dimensions to what all citizens and many professions need and must impart to librarians. In academic libraries, the learning centre movement, which places learning conditions and not just resources at the heart of its missions, is ongoing both for researchers (by offering services based on research data) and for the general public.

Accessibility and Key Programs

Both public libraries and university libraries prioritize accessibility, with one key factor being extended opening hours. According to the Observatoire de la Lecture Publique (OLP), in 2021, local authorities with over 2,000 inhabitants had an average of 20 weekly hours. However, there's a significant gap between cities, as those with over 100,000 inhabitants averaged 39.7 hours per week. Extended hours also serve as a strategy to attract more users. In 2021, the average capital expenditure per library was €29,954, translating to €312.7 per 100 inhabitants for libraries serving 2,000 or more people. Meanwhile, university libraries offer over 4,000 cultural activities and have an average weekly opening of 50 hours.

The report from the OLP stressed that, in 2021, '16% of libraries serving more than 2,000 inhabitants had implemented initiatives for people with disabilities. Unlike in the case of buildings, and just like in the case of adapted workstations and collections, this figure is very closely linked to the size of the community. Implementing cultural activities specifically aimed at people with disabilities requires training staff and the establishment of partnerships with organizations and associations specializing in this field'. At the same time, 3/4 of libraries serving at least 20,000 inhabitants are developing partnerships with associations or cultural facilities and they are organizing mostly: story reading sessions (69%) and exhibitions (62%), only 42% offer concerts and screenings, 48% book clubs, 30% parties, book fairs or festivals. This cultural offer is deeply impacted by the size of the library.

On average, a public reading establishment in a local authority with a population of over 2,000 recorded 17,161 admissions in 2021, down 16.5 points in 2019. While the pre-sanitary crisis level has not yet been reached, users are returning.

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Focus on Digital Literacy

As the principal cultural amenities and in line with its mission to contribute to the development of information literacy within the population, libraries are working to reduce the digital divide and the associated digital illiteracy (in French, the specific term is 'illectronisme' referring to the concept of illiteracy within the digital environment). According to the INSEE,³⁴ almost 15% of the French population (around 13 million people) is facing digital illiteracy. In the 2021 law, libraries are identified as an important actor to contribute to the reduction of this digital illiteracy: 'they contribute to reducing illiteracy and digital illiteracy. Through their mediation activities, they guarantee the participation and diversification of the public and the exercise of their cultural rights.' In addition, libraries were one of the potential locations for the 4,000 Digital Advisers recruited at the national level and they are well identified by the population as a place to receive support.³⁵

Through the organization of training sessions for people or the recruitment of digital mediators, libraries are tackling the subject. As digital illiteracy mainly affects the elderly and people living in rural areas, libraries, thanks to their extensive coverage, are viewed as the right vessel to touch those populations.

However, we could identify differences between libraries. Indeed, during our interviews, this question of digital illiteracy was more important for libraries within the Renne Metropole area compared to libraries from Villeneuve-d'Ascq.

Focus on Fake News

Libraries are promoting information literacy and part of this activity concerns the fight against Fake News. They are organizing workshops or creating specific content to address that question. For example, the University Library of ULille is working on the implementation of a dedicated workshop accessible to all the students of the university based on the serious game: Panique à la Rédac.³⁶

³⁴ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/7633654>

³⁵ https://labo.societenumerique.gouv.fr/documents/23/Barom%C3%A8tre_du_num%C3%A9rique_2023_-_Rapport.pdf

³⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/7024747>

2. Analysis of the case

a) Role of Libraries in Learning and Education

1) Overview

Libraries not only preserve and provide access to cultural heritage and update sources of information but also actively engage citizens through dynamic programs that foster both formal and informal learning.

To illustrate, the library of Languidic offers its members (not the general public) a community platform for knowledge exchange.³⁷ Called Steeple, this platform enables users to share hobbies, services, knowledge and know-how. Users can meet online, but also in situ, in the library, for more traditional library activities such as book clubs and makers' clubs. This platform is affiliated to the *Réseau d'Echanges Réciproques des Savoirs*. From this perspective, the library is also promoting its collections on the environment and recycling by creating a participatory vegetable garden and an 'insect hotel' with an association.³⁸

By taking into consideration the evolution of citizens' needs, libraries are evolving through new services (e.g. loans of musical instruments, works of art or a seed bank). Also, Mr Roche and Mrs Delrue emphasized the importance of mediation in regard to the general mission of learning and education. Indeed, research work or complex problems must be accompanied in order to be accessible to everyone.

Complementary to those activities, libraries are engaged in partnerships for education purposes, i.e. Public libraries with research libraries (like in Lille) to touch specific populations or to support activities. To achieve its 2030 roadmap against Fake News the ULille Research Library is partnering with Villeneuve-d'Ascq library. Indeed, they are considering that a student is first of all a citizen and that it's part of the mission of the University Library to support efforts from public libraries to develop Critical Thinking and to disseminate activities/competencies to fight against Fake News. By co-developing initiatives, they emphasize the role of libraries in promoting critical thinking and media literacy, ensuring that students and citizens alike are equipped to navigate

³⁷ <https://www.mediatheque-languidic.net/accueil/services>

³⁸ <https://www.valdesaane.com/bibliotheque-du-tortillard>

digital information responsibly. At the national level, research libraries have delivered 55,322 hours of training to 549,578 students in 2023.³⁹

At the University of Lille, the Lilliad ‘Learning Centre Innovation’ offers, in addition to the library and an events division, an activity centre showcasing research being carried out in the University’s laboratories. Open not only to researchers, but also to school and non-school groups, Xperium has been a place to visit since 2014. Doctoral students are on hand to help visitors understand research in a playful way.

Case Illustration: Xperium

Xperium is a unique concept showcasing, at the library, the research currently being conducted in the laboratories of the University of Lille. Since 2014, Xperium has been open to visitors, whether school classes or non-school groups. Doctoral students adapt their presentations to explain research in a fun and engaging way. In eleven years, Xperium has touched more than 25,000 people, 70% of whom are high school students.

Other institutions are experimenting with extended access. For example, at the Rockefeller University Health Library (University of Lyon 1), the role of documentary resources in teaching medical students has been rethought. An anatomy room (BU Santé Rockefeller), accessible 7 days a week, has been created in the library to encourage students to learn anatomy, thanks to the availability of a variety of resources (models, 3D atlases, plates, skeletons, manuals, etc.).⁴⁰

Moreover, they offer cultural and scientific mediation, as they organize exhibitions, workshops, training sessions and create meeting spaces with institutions like associations or museums. In the Rennes Metropolitan area, the library is associated with the Musée de Bretagne and a space dedicated within a specific place called Champs-Libres.⁴¹ For them, it’s an opportunity to articulate their collections to offer a broader experience. In total, almost half of the public libraries (serving more than 2,000 inhabitants) are partnering with cultural organizations.⁴²

³⁹ <https://esgbu.esr.gouv.fr/broadcast/key-figures>

⁴⁰ <https://portaildoc.univ-lyon1.fr/les-services/une-salle-danatomie-a-la-bu-sante-rockefeller>

⁴¹ <https://www.leschampslibres.fr/>

⁴² <https://www.culture.gouv.fr/Media/Thematiques/Livre-et-lecture/OLP-mediatheque/OLP-PDF/Bibliotheques-municipales-Rapport-annuel/Syntheses-nationales/synthese-nationale-donnees-d-activite-2021-des-bibliotheques-de-lecture-publique>

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2) Challenges

Among the challenges faced by libraries, the first one is that staff are under increasing pressure to juggle diverse missions, such as cultural mediation, scientific outreach, digital services, and innovative answers to social needs while dealing with declining user numbers since COVID. At the same time, librarians must adapt to rapid technological change (especially digital technologies, ecological dimension of the business) and copyright law, which requires ongoing training efforts and pedagogical methods for training collaborators but also trainers and students. For instance, training programs on digital tools and critical media analysis are becoming essential to meet the demands of a rapidly changing landscape. In addition, the staff need to be prepared in order to be able to animate a workshop or a training session.

Library managers also challenge very complex funding and policy frameworks generating strong administrative constraints. To address this, some institutions are advocating for greater autonomy and resource allocation, ensuring that libraries can fulfil their educational missions without being constrained.

Additionally, intellectual property issues require careful access to online documents, particularly when digitizing rare materials or collaborating with cultural institutions.

A last concern is collaboration between schools and libraries. Indeed, one of the interviewees stressed that: 'And when it comes to school, it's clear that we don't have the same vision. I find it difficult to reconcile the concept of education as promoted by a school system in crisis, which is unable to position itself objectively, at least in my view, in today's society. Once school is more concerned with future careers than with discovering the world, it constrains a lot of things, in terms of assessment, in a way that is more... I wouldn't say punitive, but highly restrictive, in fact. The relationship with reading is biased.' The articulation between the purpose of school and the purpose of the library should be reviewed to ensure their alignment.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries identified as actors for lifelong learning and education?	They do not directly address this goal	Through the ‘Robert law’ that states, ‘The libraries of local authorities or their associations are tasked with ensuring equal access for all to culture, information, education, research, knowledge and leisure activities, as well as promoting the development of reading.’
Are libraries part of community development plans?	Yes	Their mission is to address the needs of the population at the local, academic or national level (it depends on the kind of library).
Are libraries included in OER/Open Science/Open Data policy?	Yes (at the institutional level)	Most academic libraries, in some cases, are even leading the implementation of the policy at the level of the university. At the national level, within the committee for Open Science ⁴³ , there are librarians. In addition, the Couperin consortium ⁴⁴ is developing access to scientific and technical information for the scientific community, by facilitating national negotiations on digital documentary resources and supporting open science.

⁴³ <https://www.ovvirlascience.fr/le-comite-pour-la-science-ouverte/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.couperin.org/>

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Do libraries cooperate with schools/universities nationally or internationally?	Yes	Most of the libraries are cooperating at least with schools, and main libraries are working a lot with universities to support their training programs/workshops or cultural activities. But there is a special school library system (CDI).
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Public and Educational Impact

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Number of people visiting public libraries per year	69 million (2022)	According to the Ministry of Economy, the total number of visitors in 2022 is 69 million entries. We need to specify that, among that amount, 52 million entries are for research libraries. In 2024, 6.2 million people were registered at a public library.
Number of students/teachers visiting university libraries per year	52 million (2022)	52 million entries are for research libraries.
Academic libraries offering learning programs	Yes	Every academic library provides learning programs. In 2023, they provided 55,322 hours of training to 549,578 students.
Public libraries offering learning programs	Yes	Public libraries are offering various learning programs. It depends on the political support and the willingness of the direction and of the staff. Currently the trend is related to digital literacy. Libraries are supporting the development of this literacy in line with the needs of our society.

School libraries offering learning programs	Yes	All of them offer learning programs. Indeed, media and information literacy are part of the common foundation of knowledge, skills and culture for children. It's the school library that is in charge of providing this teaching ⁴⁵ .
Number of libraries for students	1006	1006 academic libraries are open in France.
Number of libraries for citizens	16 000	16 000 public libraries in France. In addition: CDI (school libraries) and academic libraries.
Are libraries working with NGOs, educational institutions, and associations?	Yes	<p>Libraries frequently collaborate with universities and research institutions (mostly libraries in cities with more than 2 000 inhabitants). For instance, in Paris, 'Users of Parisian libraries can now also view all the opening lectures filmed at the Collège de France since 1983, on the Parisian libraries' digital portal. These 196 exceptional documents represent milestones in the major advances in research over more than 40 years.</p> <p>This digital collection now benefits from new access and wider distribution to subscribers of Parisian libraries.⁴⁶</p> <p>Also, some libraries do partnerships with associations at the national level (such as Libraries Without Borders to develop and implement innovative</p>

⁴⁵ <https://eduscol.education.fr/1531/education-aux-medias-et-l-information>

⁴⁶ <https://www.college-de-france.fr/en/news/partnership-between-the-college-de-france-and-the-libraries-of-the-city-of-paris>

		educational and cultural policies, especially for underserved populations) or at the local level, like la Petite Bibliothèque Ronde with local cultural and art associations.
User satisfaction related to the library	Partially know	Some institutions conduct internal surveys, but there is no consolidated report at the national level: Mainly academic libraries and the National Library of France (BnF has a Public Observatory or networks of libraries)
Number of cultural or civic events hosted per year	Partially know	Number of cultural events hosted: 4000 inside university libraries in 2023. We don't know about public libraries at the national level.

b) Participation and Democratic Culture, including Social Inclusion and Equal Access

1) Overview

In France, public libraries have long served as pillars of democratic culture, embodying the principle that access to knowledge and education is a fundamental right for all citizens. As mid-19th century institutions, they emerged from a broader social movement to democratize learning and foster inclusive communities, reflecting the nation's commitment to equality and civic engagement. Today, libraries in France continue to play a critical role in promoting participation and social inclusion by ensuring equal access to resources, bridging digital divides, and creating spaces for dialogue across diverse demographics. Through programs that address marginalized groups, digital literacy initiatives, and community-driven activities, French libraries reinforce democratic values by empowering individuals to engage with society, challenge inequalities, and contribute to a more just and inclusive public life.

The move towards participation is accompanied by a greater focus on social inclusion and equal access. Libraries are seeking to diversify their audiences and break away from relying solely on the expertise of librarians by valuing the skills and knowledge of

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users, regardless of their social background or level of education. This translates into extended opening hours, greater flexibility of use, and projects aimed at reaching remote or marginalized audiences. In addition, legislation tries to reinforce the accessibility of public services⁴⁷ and inclusion. From this perspective, the French Association of Librarians has created a Charter of the fundamental right of citizens to have access to and share information and knowledge via libraries,⁴⁸ where they highlight the right of disabled people to equal and unhampered access to knowledge and information.

Among the current trends in France, we could identify the urgent question of accessibility for people with disabilities (e.g. Dyslexic, allophone public, including the accessibility of the building when it's possible) or marginalized communities. For people that are far away from libraries, some libraries do have 'bibliobus' or associated libraries to get in touch with people who are further away. However, activities like exhibitions, digital support, and workshops are mainly concentrated within the main buildings of libraries. In the specific case of libraries in prison, animations like book clubs, educational workshops, and cultural activities aim to promote literacy, reduce recidivism, and foster a sense of dignity and connection. However, access to this restricted environment remains complicated.

Atypical situations like the case of Villeneuve d'Ascq and la Petite Bibliothèque Ronde (Clamart) are interesting. Indeed, in the first case, there are the main library and associated libraries. After the 1970 merger of three cities to form Villeneuve d'Ascq, the seven existing local libraries, including their 103 benevolent, remain and collaborate with the main library. An association called B.A.V.A.R⁴⁹ was created: 'to pool resources, experiences and ideas while ensuring that each library retained its identity and characteristics inherent to its status (secular association, social centre, CBPT, and two independent libraries). The neighbourhood libraries undertook to welcome classes from local schools. Located at the heart of various communities, those libraries are deeply connected to the needs of the population and favour broad social inclusion. The issue is to ensure the quality of services and the training of benevolent people within those associated libraries.

The second case, la Petite Bibliothèque Ronde⁵⁰, is a library dedicated to early childhood and children's literature. The specificity of this library is that it was created by philanthropy and that its status allows the PBR to have a broader scope of intervention than usual. The purpose of this library is about: 'placing the child at the

⁴⁷ <https://www.info.gouv.fr/accessibilite/loi-accessibilite-cadre-legal-et-obligations>

⁴⁸ https://www.abf.asso.fr/fichiers_site/fichiers/ABF/biblib/charte_biblib_abf_uk.pdf

⁴⁹ <https://bavar.fr/index.php>

⁵⁰ <http://www.lapetitebibliothequeronde.com/>

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heart of the action, making the book an essential part of their daily life. To achieve this, we had to make the child independent and therefore give them the keys to how the establishment works, be a librarian themselves, have direct access to books, suggest activities, come up with workshops, and then seek out the skills if the librarians didn't have them'. Through this approach, we see possibilities for children to be autonomous. Moreover, as the library is located within a high priority education area, there is a very large social diversity and a possibility for local people to be invested in this cultural environment.

Finally, when it comes strictly to adapting collections to a wide audience, French public libraries have appropriated the Quebec concept of 'Facile à lire', inspired by the 'Easy-to-Read square' developed over the last twenty years in Canada, Sweden and Denmark, and boosted in France from 2014 by Livre et Lecture en Bretagne and Bibliopass. Deployed nationwide since 2018, this approach aims to promote a set of rules to facilitate comprehension of written and audio-visual communication among people who have never really mastered learning to read, or who have unlearned to read.

2) Challenges

Among the biggest challenges for libraries, we could highlight the difficulty of reaching people that are far (geographically or culturally) from libraries. Libraries need to invest to do so, yet they are currently financially constrained and they already have difficulties achieving their fundamental missions.

Through the inclusion of multiple people that work for the library (students, people with disabilities or in rehabilitation), the library is also a place of socialization. Yet, it's not easy for employees to balance that in rightful manners.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries identified by the State as a key actor to promote democratic culture?	Yes	This is clearly stated within the 'Robert law' from 2021. For the FNCC, Sylvie Robert states that the 'issue of opening up public libraries is "an essential challenge for cultural democracy and even more so for democracy in our country"'. From this

		perspective, 'The library is a unique tool that combines knowledge, expression, sharing of feelings and living together, interweaving democratization and cultural democracy.'
Are libraries promoting freedom of expression?	Yes	Yes, through their activities, exhibitions and cultural events. Some of them even offer the possibility to readers to organize an event within the library.
Are libraries integrating SDG Framework?	Partially	There was an initiative Agenda 2030 for libraries, however, it's more at the local level than something centralized. Initiatives like seed banks are created in line with ecological issues.
Are there policies in favour of social inclusion and accessibility?	Yes	<p>The question of accessibility is regulated by the State, libraries, like other public services and places that welcome people, are supposed to meet a specific standard. For online accessibility, public actors are supposed to follow the RGAA-APPS guidelines.</p> <p>The question of social inclusion is more dependent on local policies and willingness. For instance, in the north of France, libraries have created the initiative 'Bibliothèque à la maison' (library at home), a document delivery service at home.</p>
Is there a policy for people with disabilities or fewer opportunities?	Yes, partially	There is a national policy to ensure accessibility for people with disabilities. For people with fewer opportunities, the situation is less clear, as local decision makers have an important role in defining priorities.

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Are users involved in service design?	Partially	Libraries try to involve users, yet most of the time they are involved after the service design. In the case of La Petite Bibliothèque Ronde, children are associated with the creation of activities. In any case, users are almost never involved in the governance of the library.
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Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries supporting civic engagement or democratic learning?	Partially	<p>Academic and public libraries are identified as actors to support democratic learning. Through the involvement of benevolent and the organization of events related to democracy; libraries contribute to that learning. The degree of involvement of the library on this question depends on the willingness of the municipality.</p> <p>School libraries are contributing to the democratic learning of children. Their training is identified as being part of civic education.</p>
Are digital skills and AI literacy included in training?	Yes	<p>Academic, public and school libraries are well identified as an actor to train citizens, students or children about digital skills and literacy.</p> <p>For school libraries, the program is defined at the national level. For other libraries, the content of the training depends on the willingness of the direction of the library.</p>

<p>Are inclusive programs provided for vulnerable populations?</p>	<p>Partially</p>	<p>Some libraries (public and research) have introduced programs for vulnerable groups (refugees, minorities, and individuals with disabilities), yet there is no consolidated policy at the national level.</p> <p>Currently public libraries are focusing a lot over the question of disabilities, dyslexia or dyscalculia.</p>
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c) Spatial Design and Shared Spaces

1) Overview

The issues associated with library spaces and shared spaces are numerous and interconnected, reflecting the tensions between accessibility, inclusivity, and social use. In physical library spaces, challenges include managing overcrowding, designing spaces suitable for diverse audiences (children, adults, elders, etc. including people with disabilities), and promoting a balance between solitude (for reading) and conviviality (for discussions). With the development of the concept of third spaces, libraries have started to rethink spaces to achieve their purpose and give a neutral, inclusive environment that transcends traditional boundaries of home and work, fostering community, collaboration, and shared ownership of knowledge. We saw multiple examples of the development of third spaces inside libraries, like the creation of the Micro-Folie initiative that involves integrating a digital museum into existing facilities. One opportunity related to that is the culture of librarians and the fact that they are often doing a partnership with other kinds of organizations. From this perspective, they can organize shared spaces within the library to welcome those initiatives. We could identify the following types of collaborative learning spaces:

- Learning lab: Dedicated rooms equipped for active pedagogy and group projects.
- Innovation rooms: spaces focused on creativity and project-based learning.
- Group work rooms: areas specifically designed for collaborative study.
- Co-working spaces: Flexible environments that support both individual and group activities.
- Makerspaces: Workshops for collaborative creation and exploration.

As a social hub, libraries could be part of a specific commons/public partnership rooted in territories. One of the interviewees stressed that point: ‘How do you organize a seed bank? What does it mean to organize a seed bank? Does the library do everything, or does it leave room for manoeuvre, discretion and strong management of the community of residents who can work with it? Libraries are interesting spaces for this, but so are other community spaces, because they have a strong connection to the public. There is a closeness, a connection to the local area that is quite well established, and a habit of working in partnership.’ The library could be seen as ‘a public policy tool that facilitates the development of commons in a territory’. We could illustrate that aspect with the example of the Rennes Metropolitan area, where the Champs Libres managed to receive a Wikipedian during one year in residency.⁵¹ The idea was to ask him to contribute museum entries to Wikipedia, train staff and encourage the people of Rennes to get involved in Wikipedia (and, more broadly, in sharing knowledge commons).

Case Illustration: Agora (Lille)

The new research library in Social Sciences from Lille University will be called Agora⁵². By referring to this concept, architects and designers of this library would like to emphasize the position at the heart of the university and as an inclusive social space.

The new library will offer:

- A unifying space for the campus*
- A single reception desk for all campus users and a 100-seat cafeteria managed by the CROUS*
- A space for educational innovation*
- A dedicated 225 m² space, creatively integrating technology and a fully modular 70-seat collaborative workspace*
- A venue for exhibitions and cultural events*

⁵¹ <https://www.ouest-france.fr/bretagne/rennes-35000/nicolas-vigner-on-en-residence-wikipedia-au-musee-de-bretagne-pendant-un-an-32f64228-34d5-11ed-919d-c96701fa2e2f>

⁵² <https://future-bushs.univ-lille.fr/accueil>

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- An exhibition space of over 200 m², a multi-purpose event space and a 220 m² 'Quartier Libre' space
- A platform dedicated to young researchers
- A space of approximately 600 m² accessible only to doctoral students and staff, offering 80 consultation places, 4 meeting rooms and 2 project rooms

Through our interviews, the question of spatial design has a very important impact on the library and its services. All of them are currently making their spaces evolve in order to adapt them to the needs of citizens or students. Complementary to that, the Petite Bibliothèque Ronde, works a lot 'outside' of its wall: *'Why is this link with "outside the walls" so important? It is to be able to situate a cultural institution in other places of life, such as nurseries, schools and other libraries. We can also work with other libraries to encourage these complementary relationships. But the social dimension is important'*.

2) Challenges

In France, the spatial design and shared spaces in libraries are gaining increasing importance, but their implementation is currently limited. One significant challenge is the financial aspect, as transforming library spaces can be costly. This poses a significant challenge for many libraries housed in old buildings that require reorganization to meet current needs.

Furthermore, it's challenging for French libraries to allocate more space to users and empower them to make decisions and organize activities. User involvement in spatial design is also limited. While some libraries have experimented with feedback collection mechanisms, the practice of co-design (moreover involving vulnerable or marginalized groups), is not widely adopted. When we are considering giving free space to students, librarians express concern that user-driven initiatives may lack the necessary support and stability to be successful. Even in highly engaged libraries, the director still holds significant authority in governing the library. Mr Mercier was stressing that point by saying that *'Is it the library that does everything, or does it leave a great deal of room for manoeuvre, appreciation and management to the group of people who can work with it? Libraries are interesting places to do this, but in the same way as other local authorities, there is a strong link with the public. There's proximity, there's a link to the area that's quite well developed, and then there's the habit of working in partnership.'*

We could also have difficulties related to the configuration of the spaces. Indeed, the patrimonial space or research part of libraries still has important cultural barriers before being really accessible (even if they try to work on creating welcoming spaces).

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes/Sources
Are libraries building inclusive spaces?	In progress	They are currently trying to build that kind of place, yet they are restrained by administrative or financial problems.
Are libraries creating places for minorities?	Unknown	There is no policy at the national level, it depends mostly on the willingness of local decision makers. Also, the configuration of the building could be a constraint to have places for minorities.
Are libraries accessible for people with disabilities?	Yes, partially	Libraries are supposed to be accessible, like all public spaces; however, due to the austerity and difficulties inherent with the building itself, sometimes, online some disabilities will be addressed.
How many hours are libraries open?		20 h per week for small libraries, around 40 h per week for libraries in big cities and around 50h for research libraries.

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d) Digital Technologies and Information Access

1) Overview

Public libraries have increasingly embraced digital tools and open practices to enhance accessibility, foster inclusivity, and support civic engagement. Through the promotion of free software, digital literacy, open access, open science and open educational resources, libraries play an important role within the landscape of digital technologies for people. Across the years, experimentations have been done in order to touch people where they are online (e.g. around 2010 inside Facebook Groups or currently on TikTok⁵³ or Instagram⁵⁴).

An interesting example, in the Rennes Metropolitan area, the library invited a Wikipedian for one year to contribute to the life of the library. In addition, to give access to their collections, they use free software: Omeka.⁵⁵ Through this choice, they are supporting this software and contributing. The research library of Lille University is also using free software as much as possible.

The case of BiblioSésame (then Eurêkoi) is very interesting. It was an initiative set up by librarians who work on how to handle remote reception questions. In 2006, seven libraries designed an online service dedicated to answering questions from users. Their idea was: ‘to respond to people, to all audiences who came across this site in one way or another, to questions in less than 72 hours’. This project succeeds in reaching people that aren’t used to going to the library.

If we investigate more open science, open access and open data, research libraries have an important role. At Lille University, it’s the library that supports researchers to publish as openly as possible. At the national level, the co-director of the Institut National des Sciences Humaines et Sociales (INSHS) of the CNRS is a former librarian (M. Lionel Maurel). He is deputy scientific director in charge of scientific and technical information issues (including Open Science). In addition, university libraries (for instance in ULille) could lead to the development of the policy related to Open Educational Resources, Open Science and Open Data. The ministry of higher education and research is currently working on the creation of guides to support these activities and the creation of commons.⁵⁶

⁵³ <https://www.tiktok.com/@mychal3ts> or the tag booktok

⁵⁴ <https://www.instagram.com/littleprettybooks/>

⁵⁵ Omeka is an “Open-source web publishing platforms for sharing digital collections and creating media-rich online exhibits”. The software is respecting open standards like OAI-PMH or DublinCore <https://omeka.org/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/le-comite-numerique-pour-la-reussite-etudiante-et-l-agilite-des-etablissements-coreale-98527>

Case illustration: *Wikipedian residency*

(source: Nicolas Vigneron, Habib M'henni / Dyolf77, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons)

In Champs-Libre (Rennes), they received a Wikipedian for one year. This person was paid by the institution to contribute to Wikipedia and to do workshops and training sessions as much for readers/citizens as for employees of the library. The idea of this residency was to inspire new practices and a dynamic of commons and contributions.

2) Challenges

Related to the upload of content, Mr Diallo stressed that cities or libraries need to have a clear policy about what to publish and how. This is more important within the current trend of austerity. He is pushing for a more curated approach than making everything open. He is linking that dimension with the question of sobriety. Indeed, sobriety could be achieved in various ways, for instance by reducing the size/number of images or by accessing them without having them on the server.

Libraries have important challenges of visibility and discoverability of their contents. Digital tools could be a way to get in touch with public that aren't coming to the library as Mr Mercier was testifying regarding his experience *'We hadn't really targeted an audience with barriers. Instead, we tried to reach an audience that we didn't normally reach via the website. They weren't specifically excluded, they weren't the usual audience for this type of service. The experiment with Facebook groups showed us that it was quite interesting in terms of what we measured (who is asking) each time they asked a question.'*

Related to that, there is the question of interoperability between various information systems.

3) Associated Indicators

Indicator	Status	Notes / Sources
Do libraries have a role in digital skills and literacy?	Yes	Following on from the Ministry of Culture's 2018 Libraries plan ⁵⁷ , which assigned libraries the mission of "promoting digital inclusion and actions carried out in the social field", the law on libraries adopted in 2021 explicitly states that they contribute to "reducing illiteracy". In addition to that, a survey shows that 'Libraries and media libraries clearly identified by the public as places where people can learn about digital technology.'

Indicator	Status	Notes / Sources
% of electronic vs physical books	No consolidated data	We know that libraries are offering electronic resources yet there is currently no consolidated data about the amount of electronic resources vs physical resources. Libraries are often giving access to external online databases.
Availability of institutional repositories	Yes	Institutional repositories are mostly concerning research libraries. Through the creation of HAL, researchers are uploading their publications in open access. The National Library is providing a consolidated repository for notices to support the work of public libraries.

⁵⁷ <https://labo.societenumerique.gouv.fr/en/articles/folder-libraries-first-on-line-for-digital-mediation/>

<p>Availability of open-access educational/research material</p>	<p>Partial</p>	<p>Libraries in France provide significant access to open-access educational and research materials, both in academic and public settings. Indeed, through platforms like OpenEdition⁵⁸ or policies such as the 2018 National Plan for Open Science, academic libraries aim to enhance access to open-source content. Public libraries also support this effort by making open-access resources available to the greatest extent possible, contingent on factors like intellectual property constraints, as Mr. Diallo mentioned during the interview.</p>
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Indicator	Status	Notes / Sources
<p>Number of workshops/training sessions for digital literacy</p>	<p>No consolidated data</p>	<p>We know that libraries are offering training or workshops to work on question related to digital literacy yet, there is no consolidated data at the national level. In an average institution, there may be several dozen workshops a year, and on the scale of a department or network, several hundred. On a national scale, the total number of digital literacy workshops held in libraries is therefore in the thousands each year, but this estimate is indicative due to the lack of an exhaustive national census.</p>

⁵⁸ <https://www.openedition.org/>

Number of people accessing these workshops	No consolidated data	We know that libraries are offering training or workshops to work on question related to digital literacy yet, there is no consolidated data at the national level.
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Indicator	Status	Notes / Sources
% of access to digital collection	No consolidated data	We don't have a clear overview of the % of access to digital collection. This number is also related to the policy of libraries, as some of them are pushing the use of digital collection while other are more conservative. An example of access to digital collection is Gallica ⁵⁹ that has a daily audience of 60 thousand people.

⁵⁹ <https://gallica.bnf.fr/accueil/fr/html/accueil-fr>

<p>% of open access collection</p>		<p>Open access is clearly a priority within libraries, mostly in academic libraries, yet we don't have a consolidated view of this topic. According to the Ouvrir la Science, the situation is the following: 'The French Plan for Open Science has provided France with a coherent and dynamic policy in the field of open science. It was announced in 2018 by the Minister of Higher Education, Research and Innovation, Frédérique Vidal, and is coordinated by the Committee for Open Science, which brings together the Ministry, the universities and research performing organizations and the scientific community. Substantial progress has been made in the three years since this policy was introduced. The percentage of open access scientific publications in France has risen from 41% to 56%.'</p> <p>For instance, at the level of ULille research library, 73% of the publications are open.</p>
<p>Number of open datasets</p>	<p>Unknown</p>	<p>Various platforms are sharing datasets at the national level. On data.gouv.fr, more than 64,000 datasets are available. Researchers are invited to publish open datasets on platforms like Zenodo.</p>
<p>Number of Open Educational Resources (OER)</p>	<p>No consolidated data</p>	<p>The CEL⁶⁰ database is offering access to 4,164 OER. In addition, digital libraries like the BNEUF from AUF⁶¹ are aggregating thousands of pedagogical resources.</p>

⁶⁰ <https://cel.hal.science/>

⁶¹ <https://bneuf.auf.org/resource/home>

3. SWOT Analysis

Theme	Strength	Weakness	Opportunities	Threats
Role of Libraries in Learning and Education	<p>Widespread dissemination throughout the French territory.</p> <p>Specific focus over competencies like critical thinking or digital literacy.</p> <p>It's part of the librarian culture to contribute to learning and education.</p> <p>Partnerships with other educational organizations are already existing.</p>	<p>Training of librarians: they can do what they know and are able to handle.</p> <p>The number of librarians is decreasing, while the number of missions is increasing.</p> <p>There is an important disparity between small and central libraries</p>	<p>Collaboration with other knowledge organizations (e.g. museums).</p> <p>Librarians are the civil servants who undertake the most professional training.</p> <p>Librarians are already contributing to a lot of initiatives about commons, open sciences, open access or open data.</p> <p>In educational institutions, education in the commons is primarily led by teacher-librarians, even though institutional directives on the subject are silent and the involvement of these professionals remains limited.⁶²</p> <p>The essential role of the CDI (Centre de Documentation et d'Information) as a 'Common' within the school.⁶³</p>	<p>In the context of austerity, some people are pushing for paid access to libraries. This could lead to drastically reducing the accessibility of libraries.</p> <p>Dependencies to the willingness of local authorities to support this activity of learning and education.</p> <p>There is a risk that libraries will become a space for compensating for all the failings of the State, thereby putting them under pressure.</p> <p>To obtain the necessary financial and human resources to train librarian trainers.</p>

⁶² Carbillet, M & Mulot, H. (2019). *À l'école du partage : les communs dans l'enseignement*. C & F éditions, 2019. Collection « Les enfants du numérique », 302 p.

⁶³ Mahmoudi, K. (2021, mars-avril). Le CDI, Commun de l'établissement scolaire. *InterCDI*, (290), 4-8

<p>Participation and Democratic Culture, Social Inclusion and Equal Access</p>	<p>Ensuring public access to information safeguards freedom of expression, the fight against all forms of discrimination, and supports the development of a democratic society (Recommendations of the Council of Europe⁶⁴)</p> <p>Social role of libraries in France and cultural democratization. Access to collections helps combat misinformation and disinformation (example: Charte Bib'lib, Library for free access to information and knowledge⁶⁵).</p> <p>Free access to the library.</p> <p>Partnerships and initiatives to reach people far from libraries.</p> <p>Creation of specific collections for people with disabilities or specific needs.</p>	<p>How to touch people that are far from the library?</p> <p>Structural issues (e.g. buildings are not accessible, no willingness to reach specific groups of people) to provide inclusive and equal access.</p> <p>It is difficult to ask local libraries to reach out to certain audiences when they no longer have the human resources to do so.</p> <p>Difficulties to properly accommodate certain groups if librarians aren't trained for that.</p>	<p>The creation of commons/public partnerships that can be developed between libraries and various actors is a promising way of deploying the commons on a territory.</p> <p>By thinking of the library as a social hub, it could become one of the most important places for inclusion and equal access.</p>	<p>The lack of willingness or of the resources deployed to pursue this purpose.</p> <p>The lack of plans to maintain library activities during a crisis (e.g. the COVID crisis).</p> <p>Promote the concept of the library as a 'safe space' for reliable information: 'Promotion of a sustainable, reliable, and inclusive library ecosystem.' according to the Council of Europe (2023)</p>
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⁶⁴ Recommandation CM/Rec(2023)3 du Comité des Ministres aux États membres sur la législation et la politique régissant les bibliothèques en Europe (adoptée par le Comité des Ministres le 5 avril 2023 lors de la 1462e réunion des Délégués des Ministres)

⁶⁵ <https://bibliotheques-inclusives.fr/2016/04/charte-biblib-bibliotheque-pour-lacces-libre-a-linformation-et-aux-savoirs>

	<p>Third place library: social space where knowledge practices and self-care are articulated (Cf the work of Joelle Le Marec)</p> <p>The accessibility of information and knowledge is an engine of innovation and economic and social progress in the French regions.</p>			
<p>Spatial Design and Shared Spaces</p>	<p>Implementation of mediation systems (documentary and cultural) to raise awareness of works under open licences (or in the public domain) and to promote them within the library's spaces.</p>	<p>Libraries are sometimes located in old buildings that are complicated to transform and adapt them to the public of the library. Changes may cost a lot of money or if the building is classify transformations of the building could be very complicated.</p> <p>The concept of shared spaces is still complicated to implement in France, as there is a strong culture about what a library is.</p>	<p>Ongoing reflections within a lot of libraries in order to rethink the way they are organized.</p> <p>The Anglo-Saxon concept of 'learning centres', which allows rethinking library spaces and their functions, is becoming established in France (see the example of the Liliad Library⁶⁶).</p>	<p>Dissolution of the identity of the library through the evolution of space. Reduction of the number of libraries to reduce expenses.</p>
<p>Digital Technologies and Information Access</p>	<p>Libraries are already associated with important issues like Open Access, Open Science, digital literacy. It's</p>	<p>Digital resources are often unfamiliar to the general public and require the implementation of numerous</p>	<p>Taking account of alternative digital resources in documentation policies.</p> <p>Participation in</p>	<p>The digital knowledge commons still occupy a marginal position in the digital collections offered by public</p>

⁶⁶ <https://lilliad.univ-lille.fr/>

	<p>part of their missions and also part of the culture of librarians.</p> <p>Training programs and workshops are organized to address topics such as digital literacy and information literacy</p>	<p>mediation systems</p> <p>Difficulties in integrating the management of free resources into the documentary policy, unlike the paid resources of publishers</p> <p>In university research libraries, there is a discrepancy between what is said (the desire to put open access resources at the forefront) and what is done in the field (usually priority given to the management and promotion of paying scientific resources).</p> <p>Cybersecurity risks are escalating as cities and universities increasingly become targets for cybercriminals.</p>	<p>commons-oriented partnerships reinforces both the commons themselves and the social bonds within a territory</p>	<p>libraries today.</p> <p>Enclosure movement: obstacles to the circulation and sharing of information and knowledge</p> <p>Reduction of the budget to access digital content.</p> <p>The rapid and constant evolution of the digital sector, which requires regular updates.</p> <p>Regulate AI products to protect the principles of privacy and fairness.</p>
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4. Conclusion

In this initial analysis of libraries (public, research, and school), we examine their current development. France has a strong cultural tradition surrounding libraries. Librarians play a significant role in promoting free access to knowledge and education by supporting local and national initiatives. Libraries are widely distributed across the country, even though they need to strengthen collaborations with local stakeholders. They are clearly recognized as key institutions for accessing culture or specialized training, such as digital literacy.

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Issues like digital literacy and the promotion of shared resources must be addressed by library leadership, as explained by Mr. Diallo: *'This is the role I also assign myself in my directorship, which is not to confine it to a single subject explored in a corner but to support it and link it with the cultural policies of the establishment.'* This effort involves establishing dedicated infrastructure or meanings to advance these goals, which has become increasingly important in an era where austerity measures and attacks on libraries threaten their core purpose.

Libraries are expanding their missions and striving to better serve people with disabilities while evolving as community hubs. However, these transformations are more pronounced in major cities, which require substantial funding. Financial and administrative challenges remain significant obstacles for libraries aiming to meet these goals. At the same time, fostering community engagement, well-being, promoting shared resources, and education aligns with libraries' missions and serves as a strong motivator for librarians.

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Consolidated analysis

a) Key take-away

Libraries are evolving beyond traditional repositories of books to become dynamic, inclusive, and essential components of the educational and social fabric. They serve as safe, collaborative spaces for learning, critical digital literacy, and social transformation, bridging gaps in access, equity, and cultural engagement. By fostering intergenerational education, promoting open access to knowledge, and supporting digital skills, libraries contribute to democratic participation, social cohesion, and lifelong learning.

Core Strengths:

Educational Ecosystem: Libraries are integral to formal and informal education, collaborating with schools, universities, and NGOs to expand access to quality resources.

Inclusivity and Accessibility: They prioritize marginalized groups, offer tailored services (e.g., for people with disabilities), and ensure equitable access through mobile libraries and community programs.

Digital Innovation: Libraries lead in digital literacy, open access, and AI education, while addressing the digital divide through training, free resources, and hybrid models.

Key Challenges:

Underfunding and Staffing: Budget cuts, understaffing, and lack of institutional recognition threaten service quality and reach.

Inequality and Accessibility: Structural barriers (e.g., outdated infrastructure, language gaps) and regional disparities limit equitable access.

Sustainability: Reliance on temporary funding, political instability, and lack of coordination hinder long-term planning and resilience.

Opportunities for Growth:

Collaborative Governance: Strengthening community involvement, participatory planning, and partnerships with tech sectors to innovate spaces and services.

Digital Integration: Expanding open access, AI tools, and cybersecurity measures to support informed, ethical digital citizenship.

Cultural and Social Role: Reinforcing libraries as hubs for civic engagement, critical thinking, and inclusive knowledge-sharing.

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Libraries are vital to building equitable, informed, and connected societies. To fulfill their potential, they require systemic support, investment in digital resources, and a commitment to inclusivity, ensuring they remain relevant in a rapidly changing world.

b) In deep analysis

Role of Libraries in Learning and Education

With regard to this axis, it should be noted that libraries are defined as a space for non-formal and intergenerational education, with a role in the educational ecosystem. Beyond encouraging reading, libraries are being redefined as safe havens and meeting places, living tools for social transformation that foster the creation of collective knowledge, critical digital literacy and the promotion of cultural rights. The alliance with schools, secondary schools and universities promotes access to quality education, although there is still progress to be made in collaboration with universities.

The adaptation of libraries to their immediate social context has led them to offer services such as tutoring classes, language exchanges and collaborative learning spaces. This evolution has been accompanied by the appearance of new professional profiles and multidisciplinary teams, such as educators and social educators and cultural facilitators.

Among the challenges faced by the educational role of libraries is the need to expand their pedagogical functions by consolidating themselves as spaces for learning and holistic development, increasing the dissemination of their services in multiple formats to reach all citizens, fostering more alliances with local organizations, and defining qualitative indicators to assess their impact.

Strengths

The consolidated analysis highlights a robust academic library infrastructure characterized by initiatives such as HEAL-Link, Open Access (Greece), and repositories such as Hal (France). Research libraries actively participate in national and international networks like OpenAIRE and LIBER, fostering collaboration on a broader scale. Educational efforts include MOOCs, information literacy programs, and digital skills workshops, which enhance learning beyond traditional formal education settings. Specific model libraries, such as Perrotis Library and the University of Patras Library in Greece, exemplify effective practices in academic and community engagement.

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Libraries serve as spaces for informal intergenerational education, playing a central role within the broader educational ecosystem. They function as living machines of social transformation, encouraging reading, knowledge production, and cultural rights. Depending on the country, the library system is mature and resilient, with strong leadership. For instance, in France, widespread dissemination underscores their geographic impact.

The focus on competencies like critical thinking and digital literacy highlights the library's role in developing essential skills. Inherently part of librarian culture, libraries contribute to learning and education through their services and partnerships with other educational organizations. This collaborative approach strengthens their relevance and effectiveness within societal contexts.

Weaknesses

The analysis underscores several critical challenges within librarianship. Insufficient training opportunities for professionals highlight a lack of investment in their professional development (Greece), while the demand for skilled workers continues to grow. This imbalance is exacerbated by declining numbers of trained staff despite increasing responsibilities, creating a strain on service quality. Additionally, disparities between small and central libraries persist, leading to chronic understaffing issues that hinder equitable access to resources. In Greece, the absence of a coordinated national strategy that recognizes libraries as integral educational institutions further compounds these problems.

Moreover, there is a noticeable unevenness in service quality and accessibility across different regions, contributing to systemic inequities. The limited integration of certified educational programs into schools and public libraries exacerbates these issues by failing to provide comprehensive learning opportunities. Poorly defined missions within the profession also contribute to confusion about their role in society, while the lack of qualitative evaluation indicators makes it difficult to assess the effectiveness of library services. Furthermore, the lack of institutional recognition for their educational responsibilities, as well as inadequate inter-institutional collaboration, prevent them from creating a unified approach to library services. Finally, precarious working conditions for librarians undermine their ability to provide high-quality services, further highlighting the need for systemic reform.

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Opportunities

The integration of libraries into lifelong learning and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) strategies is crucial for fostering educational initiatives and cultural dissemination. Collaboration with schools, universities, NGOs, and other institutions like museums extends the scope of library functions, enhancing digital education and community learning policies. The development of a national platform supports these efforts, leveraging online training courses to reach broader audiences.

Librarians play a vital role as civil servants requiring professional training, contributing significantly to commons initiatives, open sciences, and open data. However, in educational settings, teacher-librarians often lead commons education without adequate institutional support. The CDI (Centre de Documentation et d'Information) stands out as a key resource within schools, emphasizing its role as supporting commons, learning and collaboration.

Threats

The analysis highlights several critical challenges faced by libraries under austerity measures. Paid access initiatives risk reducing accessibility, while local authorities' support is a key dependency. Libraries may become overburdened, as state failures are compensated for, adding strain. The necessity for financial and human resources to train librarians underscores potential staffing issues. Political changes might deprioritize education, leading to underfunding, and budget cuts targeting educational programs exacerbate these challenges.

Reliance on volunteers can be unsustainable during austerity, while declining physical loans suggests reduced usage. External or temporary funding sources make institutions unstable, compounded by institutional neglect and lack of long-term planning. Expertise loss due to retirement without replacement further threatens library operations. These interrelated issues collectively highlight the fragile state of libraries under current conditions.

Participation and Democratic Culture, Including Social Inclusion and Equal Access

Regarding democratic culture and inclusion in libraries, this is reflected in diverse and meaningful experiences, such as the commitment to collaborative sharing of resources and the creation of thematic communities, as well as mobile libraries, which ensure territorial equity in access to culture and knowledge.

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Also on an international level, as shown by the interviews conducted, the library emerges as a safe, inclusive and welcoming space, especially for vulnerable groups or those in situations of displacement.

This protective and democratic role -safeguarding the right to information and non-discrimination- consolidates the library as an irreplaceable public institution in building more cohesive, diverse and fairer societies.

Among the challenges, three areas appear as priorities: guaranteeing real inclusion in cultural diversity, strengthening models of participatory governance with the community, and providing libraries with the necessary human and technical resources to deploy their transformative potential. All of this, without forgetting the need for a firm stance to preserve their role as safe, free and democratic spaces.

Strengths

Libraries play a crucial role in fostering democratic development by ensuring free and equitable access to information, thereby safeguarding freedom of expression and combating discrimination. This is supported by the Recommendations of the Council of Europe, emphasizing libraries as instruments for cultural democratization and public education. Access to collections helps combat misinformation and disinformation, exemplified by initiatives like Charte Bib'lib, which prioritizes free access to knowledge and information.

Libraries offer free access to resources and engage in partnerships and outreach initiatives to reach marginalized or distant communities. They also create specialized collections tailored to individuals with disabilities or specific needs, ensuring inclusivity. The concept of third-place libraries extends beyond traditional spaces, integrating knowledge practices and self-care into community hubs.

These institutions drive innovation and economic progress in regions through accessible information and foster social cohesion by supporting vulnerable groups such as refugees, LGBTQ+, and people with disabilities. Libraries serve as civic spaces for expression and community-based programs, fostering engagement and collaboration. Strong local partnerships with NGOs and other stakeholders enhance their impact, positioning libraries as essential hubs for democratic discourse and societal well-being.

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Weaknesses

To reach people who are far from the library, structural issues such as inaccessible buildings, lack of resources, and insufficient librarian training pose significant challenges. Libraries may struggle to accommodate certain groups if there is no willingness to extend services to them, and this can create barriers to inclusivity and equal access. Additionally, without a national framework for civic engagement through libraries, uneven implementation of accessibility technologies, limited multilingual and intercultural content, and a lack of standardized indicators to measure participation, it becomes difficult to ensure that libraries effectively reach marginalized communities.

These systemic issues highlight the need for improved planning, training, and resource allocation to overcome barriers and enhance library services. Without addressing these challenges, libraries risk falling short of their potential to serve as inclusive spaces that foster civic engagement and community well-being.

Opportunities

The transformation of libraries into dynamic community hubs offers a promising approach to deploying common resources effectively across territories. By repositioning libraries as social spaces, they can become central platforms for fostering inclusion, equality, and civic engagement. This shift involves not only providing access to books but also hosting various social activities, educational programs, and cultural events that engage diverse groups within the community. To support this vision, formal policy recognition by governments or institutions is crucial. Such recognition would allocate resources, establish specific programs, and create guidelines that champion libraries as inclusive spaces for democratic education. Additionally, accessing EU funds for civic initiatives can provide the necessary financial backing to expand and enhance these efforts.

The development of user engagement metrics and participatory service design further ensure that libraries effectively meet community needs. By tracking usage patterns and implementing tailored services, libraries can identify gaps and improve their offerings, ultimately demonstrating their impact on social cohesion and community well-being. This comprehensive approach positions libraries as vital hubs for fostering connection, learning, and collective action within the territory.

The creation of commons/public partnerships that can be developed between libraries and various actors is a promising way of deploying the commons on a territory.

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Threats

The lack of willingness or resources to pursue library purposes, coupled with inadequate crisis management plans (such as during the COVID pandemic), highlights systemic weaknesses in library operations. While efforts to promote a sustainable, reliable, and inclusive library ecosystem have been made, as emphasized by the Council of Europe in 2023, these initiatives risk leading to social exclusion if inclusion efforts remain fragmented and under-resourced. Additionally, an overreliance on personal initiative rather than systemic support creates gaps in ensuring equitable access and effective community engagement, further complicating efforts to achieve inclusive library services.

Spatial Design and Shared Spaces

In relation to the spatial design of libraries, this has become a key issue in addressing contemporary social and cultural challenges. The notion of spatial neutrality is called into question, as library environments often reproduce internal segregation, architectural barriers or institutional control dynamics.

There is a growing call to move towards more open, flexible and inclusive models that support diverse uses and encourage social cohesion. While there is a recognized need to expand training areas and collaborative workspaces, there is also evidence of the positive impact of itinerant pedagogy in contexts lacking infrastructure. Furthermore, various initiatives highlight the value of decentralization and engagement with local organizations, although the absence of a central coordinating space remains a challenge.

The overall challenge is to conceive libraries as spaces for shared learning, underpinned by community-led management and reduced dependence on hierarchical structures.

Strengths

The implementation of mediation systems focused on open licences and works in the public domain aims to raise awareness and promote these resources within library spaces. This initiative fosters inclusivity by creating flexible, multi-purpose areas tailored for diverse user groups, serving as hubs for community engagement and civic participation. Libraries are highlighted as vital democratic institutions, playing a key role in cultural life and reducing inequalities through accessible, collaborative learning commons and zones.

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Additionally, enhancing accessibility within libraries is crucial, with features like ergonomic furniture, proper lighting, and ramps ensuring that spaces are usable for all. Libraries also participate in innovative spatial projects to further support cultural, educational, and social development.

Weaknesses

Libraries face significant challenges due to their often-outdated locations in older buildings, which are costly and complex to adapt to modern needs. Small libraries frequently encounter physical space limitations, hindered by architectural constraints that impede flexibility. Additionally, some areas within libraries remain underused or controlled by bureaucratic regulations, and internal segregation, such as separate reading and activity zones, can limit functionality. The concept of shared spaces remains difficult to implement in France, influenced by a strong cultural perception of what a library should be.

Community involvement is also an issue, as libraries often lack visibility and struggle to engage less involved groups. Infrastructure inequality persists, particularly in rural and school settings, where resources may be scarce. Furthermore, staff training in space planning, accessibility, and user involvement is lacking, contributing to minimal participatory planning with user communities. These factors collectively hinder the library's role as a dynamic, inclusive space for all.

Opportunities

Libraries play a pivotal role as safe spaces for fostering debate, community expression, and social cohesion. They serve as civic reference points, bringing together diverse groups to promote unity and shared values. To enhance this role, libraries are redefining their governance processes by involving users actively, moving away from a passive model. This shift encourages community participation in library operations and decision-making.

To support these efforts, partnerships with public institutions and national guidelines ensure that library spaces are inclusive, adaptable, and co-designed with the community. These initiatives leverage funding from EU sources and foundations to upgrade physical infrastructure, while collaborations with architecture and design schools bring innovative spatial concepts to the table. Ongoing reflections within libraries about their organization highlight a commitment to continuous improvement and relevance.

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The concept of ‘learning centres,’ inspired by Anglo-Saxon models like the Liliad Library (France), is gaining traction in Europe, offering fresh perspectives on library functions and spaces. This approach emphasizes versatility and redesign, allowing libraries to adapt to changing community needs. By extending the number of spaces and collaborating with neighbouring facilities, libraries are creating multifaceted hubs that cater to diverse activities and groups.

Efforts are also focused on improving the management of shared learning spaces, ensuring efficient use of resources for various purposes, from study areas to community meetings. These initiatives underscore a broader vision: transforming libraries into dynamic, inclusive spaces that drive innovation, social cohesion, and civic engagement.

Threats

The analysis reveals several critical challenges affecting libraries, including a lack of resources and unwillingness to commit to their purposes, which hinder their effectiveness. Libraries face inadequate planning and preparedness for crises like the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting potential operational vulnerabilities.

Promoting libraries as safe spaces for reliable information is crucial, as emphasized by the Council of Europe (2023), yet this identity is being eroded by evolving physical spaces and reductions in library numbers to save costs. Institutional control over public spaces and pressure from incompatible multiple uses risk underutilization, leading to abandoned or neglected facilities.

Threats such as attacks and censorship by reactionary groups, coupled with political disengagement, further complicate library operations. The perception of libraries as welfare services may reduce their proactive role in communities. Additionally, innovation fatigue without institutional and financial backing threatens libraries’ ability to adapt and grow. These factors collectively underscore the need for sustainable strategies to ensure libraries remain vital community assets.

Digital Technologies and Information Access

Libraries have had to reinvent themselves to cope with technological change and guarantee equal access to digital resources. In addition to offering online tools and services, they play a fundamental role in digital literacy and critical thinking in the face of misinformation and the use of AI.

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Despite these advances, access inequalities persist – particularly in the form of the digital divide, which manifests across generational and cultural lines, limiting the participation of significant segments of the population. Initiatives such as the prescription of educational video games and critical reflection on Internet use illustrate a commitment to tackle these challenges from an inclusive and educational lens. However, the lack of resources and the need to complement digital communication with printed materials highlight the reality that parts of the population still lack access to digital services.

Libraries thus remain key spaces for fostering critical digital citizenship, yet additional resources, training and tools are needed to make this possible.

Strengths

Libraries play a crucial role in advancing initiatives such as Open Access and Open Science, which are integral to their missions and cultural priorities. Through organized training programs and workshops, libraries focus on enhancing digital literacy and information literacy, striving to provide equal and free access to digital resources. Critical information literacy is also emphasized, ensuring that individuals can navigate and evaluate information effectively.

The emphasis on critical thinking and problem-solving skills equips professionals with the ability to discern reliable sources, fostering informed decision-making within society. This commitment underscores libraries' dedication to building accessible, educated communities, thereby promoting cultural and intellectual growth.

Weaknesses

The challenges facing the integration and management of digital resources highlight several critical barriers. Digital resources remain unfamiliar to many users, necessitating mediation systems to guide their access and usage. The integration of free resources into documentary policies is particularly difficult compared to the more structured approach with paid publisher resources. Additionally, there is a discrepancy between the stated goal of prioritizing open access resources in university libraries and the current practice, which often focuses on managing and promoting paid scientific resources.

Furthermore, digital training remains insufficient, leaving users ill-equipped to navigate and effectively utilize modern technologies. The limited development of critical AI tools exacerbates these challenges, hindering efficient resource management and analysis.

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High levels of digital literacy among users also impede effective resource utilization, as they may lack the necessary skills to access, authenticate, or properly apply technological resources. Obsolete technological infrastructure further complicates these efforts, leading to inefficiencies and limitations in service delivery. These interconnected issues underscore the need for comprehensive strategies to enhance digital resource management, improve user access and training, and strengthen cybersecurity measures. Regarding cybersecurity, threats are rising as cities and universities become increasingly targeted by cybercriminals, posing risks to digital assets and data integrity.

Opportunities

The integration of alternative digital resources into documentation policies is crucial for fostering comprehensive and adaptable strategies. By participating in partnerships and collaborative efforts, communities can strengthen shared resources and build stronger relationships within their territories, ensuring a diverse and sustainable knowledge base.

Enhancing digital literacy through targeted training programs and investing in AI-driven technological projects are essential steps toward improving access to and management of digital resources. These initiatives help create mechanisms to identify and disseminate reliable information, even in the face of overwhelming data volumes, while fostering innovation and collaboration with local tech entities. Together, these efforts contribute to a more informed and connected community.

Threats

The digital knowledge commons remain underrepresented in public library collections, reflecting a failure to prioritize open access and collaborative resource sharing. The enclosure movement continues to impose barriers on information and knowledge circulation, restricting access and collaboration. Libraries face challenges in accessing digital content due to budget constraints, while the rapid evolution of technology requires continuous updates and adaptability. Additionally, there is an urgent need to regulate AI products to ensure they uphold principles of privacy and fairness. Technological dependence further complicates matters when paired with insufficient training support, exacerbating disparities in digital literacy. These issues highlight a persistent digital divide, hindering equal access to resources and opportunities.

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General Conclusion

The LibCommon project, funded by Erasmus+, aims to stimulate innovative learning and teaching practices in higher education by reimagining and refiguring libraries as commons-based learning hubs. This approach leverages formal and non-formal education to develop essential competencies for today's complex society, including civic engagement, participatory citizenship, intercultural and intergenerational skills, openness to lifelong learning, critical thinking, and digital competences. In this deliverable, we conducted three in-depth analyses in Greece, Spain, and France to gain an overview of the situation and identify gaps and needs. To achieve this, partners conducted interviews and a literature review of national and international reports. All materials were analyzed through a SWOT analysis.

The current state of libraries in Greece, Spain, and France highlights both their potential and enduring challenges.

In Greece, structural limitations, such as underfunding, inadequate digital infrastructure, and insufficient professional development, hinder the sector's progress. Despite efforts toward modernization and open practices, collaboration among libraries remains crucial for effective operation. Interviews emphasize the need for regional mapping to identify opportunities for partnerships with schools and domain-specific networks, such as health information services, to bridge spatial and technological disparities in underserved areas. Additionally, in all interviews, the need of staffing in all libraries with newly qualified professionals was emphasized. Here we would add the urgent need to create organized school libraries by hiring qualified librarians. A consistent national policy on libraries is essential, aligned with both the EU's library framework and the commons-based logic that promotes inclusivity, fairness, and modernization. This alignment would guarantee equitable access to knowledge and cultural resources, reinforcing democratic values, shared public responsibility, and innovative teaching and learning practices in Universities and in formal education in general.

In Spain, libraries are undergoing a transition from traditional roles as book repositories to more community-oriented spaces, aligning with the IFLA Manifesto's vision. This shift is exemplified by initiatives fostering shared learning, community engagement, and well-being. Libraries are now trying, in this perspective, to be a safe space with a positive impact on the education of citizens (such as for digital literacy). Yet, they are facing at the same time difficulties related to the degradation of their work environment, the lack of recognition regarding their educational missions and their dependance on political support. There are, even, attacks from reactionary groups

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against the library and its missions. While there is a growth of individualism, and less engagement within libraries, the common perspective could be a way to revitalise them and foster diversity among the public.

In France, libraries benefit from a strong tradition and robust infrastructure. As the most widespread cultural institution, they significantly influence education and support democratic culture. However, the number of librarians is declining, while their responsibilities are expanding. This trend has led to growing tensions among staff, exacerbated by administrative burdens that limit their ability to innovate or take initiative. Even though libraries are well-established in their communities, strengthening partnerships with other cultural and artistic organizations could further benefit the public. Libraries are familiar with the concept of common and could be an interesting actor to promote this approach at the local level, yet challenges like shared governance remain obstacles. Libraries already play a key role in education, with a focus on digital literacy. National programs apply to school libraries, but public and research libraries depend largely on local leadership. A national policy could ensure consistent access to these services across the country.

Despite these advancements, challenges persist. Klininberg (2020) highlights the potential of libraries as commons, yet a SWOT analysis reveals significant obstacles. Richard Sennett's (2021) insights into coexistence and interaction among diverse groups underscore the complexity of fostering shared dynamics and building shared spaces. Within the perspective of Ostrom and Bollier, libraries should evolve into self-governed, open goods that promote diverse community bonds and counteract neoliberal instrumentalism. Indeed, the library alone isn't going to solve all people's issues yet by joining its strengths in vessels like common joint partnerships.

The LibCommon project assumes particular relevance here, offering a framework for advancing libraries as inclusive, knowledge-driven institutions. Given global challenges, including the rise of neo-fascism, safeguarding libraries' existing roles has become increasingly vital. This underscores the need for a coordinated national strategy in Greece, cross-sectoral policy alignment in Spain to support library development and collaboration and a more coordinated approach in France. The LibCommon project underscores the importance of viewing libraries as common good, integral to all types of education – formal, non-formal, and informal.

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